

ADVAGEN

DELIVERABLE REPORT

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Project summary

This report is part of the deliverables from the project "ADVAGEN" (Development of ADVAnced next GENeration Solid-State batteries for Electromobility Applications), which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 101069743.

To date, the battery market is dominated by lithium-ion (Li-ion) chemistries, as the energy density has more than doubled, and their costs have dropped by a factor of at least 10. However, conventional Li-ion batteries (LIB) are reaching their performance limits in terms of energy density and facing safety issues required the development and production of new battery generations, such as Solid-State Batteries (SSBs), to create a new industry value chain in Europe towards their commercialization. Consequently, high-energy-density EU-made SSBs will ensure the supply of, among others, the automotive sector. To do so, the development and deployment of new manufacturing technologies, enabling the large-scale production of SSBs, is crucial. Indeed, among the overarching themes to develop and produce sustainable batteries in the future, the BATTERY 2030+ roadmap considers manufacturability as a cross-cutting key area. Innovative and scalable manufacturing techniques to produce SSBs will accelerate cost reduction, energy savings, and enhanced safety. ADVAGEN will develop a new lithium metal (LiM) battery cell technology based on a safe, reliable, and high performing hybrid solid-state electrolyte (LLZO-LPS based), gaining a competitive advantage over the worldwide (mainly Asian) competition. This will sustainably strengthen the EU as a technological and manufacturing leader in batteries as specified in the ERTRAC electrification roadmap and SET-Plan Action Point-7. ADVAGEN consortium contains key EU actors in the battery sector, from industrial materials producers (CPT, ABEE), battery manufacturer (ABEE) to R&D centers (IKE, CEA, IREC, TUB, CICE, POLITO, INEGI, UL, FEV) and the automotive industry (TME), covering the complete knowledge and value chain. By developing high-performance, affordable and safe batteries, ADVAGEN aims to re-establish European competitiveness in battery cell production.

Objective and Executive summary

The deliverable D2.2 corresponds to the main outcome of task 2.2, titled "Ecodesign guidelines". These guidelines present the best practices for materials, energy and emissions for ecodesign of the SSB cell and battery module technology, including market applications. Within the scope of the ADVAGEN project, the guidelines consider the entire life cycle of the SSB. The main goal is to provide impactful measures to prevent and mitigate the environmental impacts of SSBs and to extend the useful lifetime of SSBs and their critical raw materials. These measures are to be taken into consideration by the consortium during the development of the ADVAGEN SSB technology, specifically for the cell components and materials that affect the manufacturing process and assembly, use phase and end-of-life treatment. Firstly, a comprehensive review of the current literature on SSB environmental performance was conducted, including also cost reduction measures. The review included current and upcoming policies for lithium-ion batteries, as well as future regulation requirements. Based on the literature review and the regulatory trends, a set of ecodesign parameters that can apply to SSBs was selected. Then, ADVAGEN expert insights were presented, providing recommendations to overcome the technical and market challenges for improving the identified parameters in the SSB design. The gathered recommendations were then transformed into specific life cycle ecodesign guidelines for SSBs.

List of partners

N°	Name	Short name	Country
1	AVESTA BATTERY & ENERGY ENGINEERING	ABEE	BE
2	INEGI - INSTITUTO DE CIENCIA E INOVACAO EM ENGENHARIA MECANICA E ENGENHARIA INDUSTRIAL	INEGI	PT
3	POLITECNICO DI TORINO	POLITO	IT
4	FEV EUROPE GMBH	FEV	DE
5	COMMISSARIAT A L ENERGIE ATOMIQUE ET AUX ENERGIES ALTERNATIVE	CEA	FR
6	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET BRAUNSCHWEIG	TUBS	DE
7	CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION COOPERATIVA DE ENERGIAS ALTERNATIVAS FUNDACION, CIC ENERGIGUNE FUNDAZIOA	CICE	ES
8	FUNDACIO INSTITUT DE RECERCA DE L'ENERGIA DE CATALUNYA	IREC-CERCA	ES
9	TOYOTA MOTOR EUROPE NV	TME	BE
10	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJAN	UL	SI
11	EUROQUALITY SARL	EQY	FR
12	TECHCONCEPTS BV	TC	NL
13	CERAMIC POWDER TECHNOLOGY AS	CERPOTECH	NO
14	IKERLAN S. COOP	IKERLAN	ES

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List of abbreviations

ADR	European Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Road
CAM	Cathode Active Materials
CEAP	Circular Economy Action Plan
CF	Carbon Footprint
CRM	Critical Raw Materials
CRMA	Critical Raw Materials Act
DPP	Digital Product Passport
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
ErPs	Energy-Related Products
ESPR	Ecodesign For Sustainable Products Regulation
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
IRA	The Inflation Reduction Act
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LIB	Lithium-Ion Batteries
Li-M	Lithium-Metal
NMP	N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PEIS	Potentiostatic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy
PFA	Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
p-LCA	Prospective Life Cycle Assessment
PVDF	Polyvinylidene fluoride
R&D	Research & Development
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals
SE	Solid Electrolyte
SOCE	State of certified energy
SoH	State-of-Health
SSB	Solid-State Batteries
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WFD	Waste Framework Directive

1. Introduction

The development of the 4th lithium-ion battery generation, based on solid-state batteries (SSB) technology, and their use for electric mobility applications is a long-awaited milestone for the European Union Green Deal objectives, where it is expected that the new advantages brought by SSB technology will support a more robust deployment of electric vehicles (EVs) into European roads¹. This new generation is projected to bring several advantages compared to current LIBs^{2,3}. SSB technology is expected to be safer due to the solid-state electrolyte (SSE), which increases thermal stability and does not have the risk of explosion in crash situations or due to overheating. This, in turn, can lead to higher safety usability for EVs, which have been limited in their performance when in extreme weather conditions. In addition, the reduced risk for thermal runaway and explosions increases the expected battery lifetime for EV use and even empowers second-life applications, such as stationary use for renewable energy grid support. The higher energy density is expected to increase vehicle range for the same volume or weight, and the greater ionic conductivity can reduce charging time for EVs. The increased lifetime and energy density of SSBs have also the potential to reduce their life cycle environmental impacts. However, the SSB technology is still under development, with several challenges to overcome regarding the material alternatives for the SSE and the anode, including potential unwanted reactions in the interface². In addition, the recycling of SSB is yet to be established due to the low maturity level of development, leading to high uncertainty when it comes to the final designs that will be made available in the market. Nonetheless, the present state of development can allow for the integration of non-conventional parameters, such as environmental performance, into the design of future SSBs. By implementing environmental mitigation actions that consider the whole life cycle of the SSB technology, from extraction to production and end-of-life, it is possible to combine optimal functionality with low environmental impacts.

Ecodesign has become an important approach in innovation for sustainable technology by integrating environmental performance parameters into the design phase of a product or system from a life cycle thinking perspective, allowing for new solutions to emerge that not only meet the technical requirements but also reduce or prevent the potential environmental impacts that occur in a product's lifetime. In fact, ecodesign is the act of minimising the environmental impacts while maintaining or even increasing the functionality, as only useful and valued products can claim to be sustainable, as cited in Mogensen & Rouse⁴.

Integrating ecodesign principles and mindset into the development of SSBs is vital, as the reduced environmental impacts can support a more resilient and cleaner value chain for batteries, ensuring that the deployed technology can be an ally to the net-zero European transport sector ambitions. In the context

¹ Bielewski, M., A. Pfrang, S. Bobba, A. Kronberga, A. Georgakaki, S. Letout, A. Kuokkanen, et al. 2022. "Clean Energy Technology Observatory: Batteries for Energy Storage in the European Union - 2022 Status Report on Technology Development, Trends, Value Chains and Markets." Luxembourg. <https://doi.org/10.2760/808352>.

² Mizuno, Fuminori, Chihiro Yada, and Hideki Iba. 2014. Solid-State Lithium-Ion Batteries for Electric Vehicles. Lithium-Ion Batteries: Advances and Applications. Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-59513-3.00012-1>.

³ Sun, Yang Kook. 2020. "Promising All-Solid-State Batteries for Future Electric Vehicles." ACS Energy Letters 5 (10): 3221–23. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsenerylett.0c01977>.

⁴ Mogensen, Anna, and Gwenaelle Rouse. 2012. "Paths to Improving the Environmental Performance of Lithium-Ion Batteries: From Eco-Design to Eco-Innovation." In 2012 Electronics Goes Green 2012+, 1–6. Berlin, Germany: IEEE. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?tp=&number=6360548&isnumber=6360408>.

of the ADVAGEN project and in line with Objective 4 to “**Develop safer handling and recovery of various metals through sustainable recycling process (environmental impact and cost estimate**”, specifically “*Eco-design and recycling will be taken into account in all stages of the process and ADVAGEN aims to reach 90% recovery of critical raw materials (CRM’s) and 95% selectivity of CRM’s in leaching process, leading to a reduction of 20% of CO₂eq. emissions of batteries*”, this deliverable collects the main literature, policy and expert recommendations for a more sustainable design for SSBs, to support technology developers, policy makers and the stakeholders of the European battery value chain.

1.1 Methodological Approach Framework

Ecodesign is a systematic approach standardised by ISO 14006⁵ to implement environmental considerations into product design and development. Through a life cycle thinking perspective, ecodesign allows the prevention or mitigation of potential environmental impacts that occur throughout the life cycle of a product, from raw material extraction to end-of-life treatment, by implementing design decisions to enhance functional and environmental performance. The combination of ecodesign approaches with the environmental performance characterisation that is obtained from the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology has allowed for a broader view of the potential environmental impacts beyond the scope of the product designer, which is usually restrictively focused on the production and use phase. In addition, potential recommendations for design based on LCA can cause an effective reduction in the life cycle impacts. The availability of battery information regarding functional and environmental performance can be a tool for stakeholders across the battery value chain to decide on the best pathways for each SSB model, which is in line with the upcoming digital battery passport⁶.

The recommendations gathered from existing legislative requirements and regulations for ecodesign and lithium-ion batteries for EVs, combined with the expertise provided by the ADVAGEN partners and the existing literature on LCA and ecodesign studies for the potential environmental performance of SSB for electric vehicle applications, will serve as a basis for the main outline of the SSB ecodesign guidelines. Figure 1 showcases the framework for the development of the ecodesign guidelines.

⁵ ISO 14006. 2020. “Environmental Management Systems — Guidelines for Incorporating Ecodesign.” International Organization for Standardization. <https://www.iso.org/standard/72644.html>.

⁶ European Parliament; Council of the European Union. (2023). Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 of the European Parliament and of the council of 12 July 2023 concerning batteries and waste batteries, amending Directive 2008/98/EC and Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 and repealing Directive 2006/66/EC. Official Journal of the European Union, L 191, 1-117. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/1542/oj>

Framework for SSB Ecodesign guidelines

Figure 1 - Development framework for the guidelines.

In pursuit of a low-carbon transport sector, the legislative landscape is going through significant changes that affect battery products and battery materials. These rapid changes can create challenges for technology developers who need a stable framework to strategize future designs and applications. Nonetheless, it is crucial that regulatory documents are keeping pace with evolving technology and societal necessities. As such, the presented guidelines were developed based on the two main official legal documents related to ecodesign and electric vehicle (EV) batteries: the ecodesign Directive⁷ and the batteries Directive⁸. Both the versions in force and the new versions, i.e., the Regulation for Batteries⁶ and the new Ecodesign Regulation^{9,10} were considered. This will allow to incorporate the new strategies and upcoming challenges targeted for the future lithium-ion batteries, including SSB technology.

Other relevant reports from governmental and scientific bodies were also considered in order to establish a scope of action, as well as a structure for the overall objective of the guidelines. The analysis of these

⁷ European Parliament; Council of the European Union. (2009). Directive 2009/125/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 October 2009 establishing a framework for the setting of ecodesign requirements for energy-related products (recast). Official Journal of the European Union, L 285, 10–35. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2009/125/2012-12-04>

⁸ European Parliament; Council of the European Union. (2006). Directive 2006/66/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 September 2006 on batteries and accumulators and waste batteries and accumulators and repealing Directive 91/157/EEC. Official Journal of the European Union, L 266, 1–14. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2006/66/2018-07-04>

⁹ European Commission. 2022. Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council Establishing a Framework for Setting Ecodesign Requirements for Sustainable Products and Repealing Directive 2009/125/EC. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2022:0142:FIN>.

¹⁰ European Parliament; Council of the European Union. 2024. Regulation (EU) 2024/1781 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 Establishing a Framework for the Setting of Ecodesign Requirements for Sustainable Products, Amending Directive (EU) 2020/1828 and Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 and Repeal. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1781/oj>.

documents will identify requirements that are potentially applicable to the design, performance and specifications for the case study of electric vehicle batteries. Then, the ADVAGEN partners analysed these requirements based on their stakeholder activities. The discussions allowed to identify the main obstacles related to each parameter (both technical and market-wise) and, together with the information obtained in the current state-of-art, the guidelines were built for the ecodesign of solid-state cells in order to support cell designers and battery stakeholders, namely through the identification of relevant data that should be made available throughout the SSB life cycle through the upcoming Digital Battery Passport.

1.2 Main objectives and structure

This document - D2.2: Eco-design guidelines, presents guidelines on the best practices for materials, energy, and emissions for cell and module ecodesign. These guidelines will support the developers during the manufacturing phase in considering the environmental and economic parameters in the conceptualisation of the cell and battery module's final design. This report is the final result of task 2.2 Eco-design guidelines.

Structure of the document

The present deliverable is organised as follows:

- **Introduction:**
 - Methodological approach framework: presents the main framework to develop the ecodesign guidelines
 - Main objectives and structure of this document
- **Ecodesign parameters:**
 - Current State-of-Art – assessment of current literature on LIBs, focusing on identifying the main conclusions and recommendations, as well as gaps, weaknesses, and risks for SSB environmental and economic performance
 - Regulatory trends towards sustainable European batteries – explores relevant European policies and legislation towards the sustainability of batteries
 - Other market trends – it explores relevant policies and legislation of the main battery manufacturers countries, such as China and the U.S.A.
 - Ecodesign parameters for batteries – collected ecodesign parameters applicable to SSBs
- **ADVAGEN battery stakeholder recommendations:**
 - Challenges for ADVAGEN stakeholders – recommendations & expectations – presents the SSB challenges, recommendations and expectations from the ADVAGEN battery stakeholders, including conflicting recommendations
- **Ecodesign guidelines for Solid-State Batteries:**
 - Guidelines – identified ecodesign guidelines for SSBs in the context of the ADVAGEN project
- **Conclusion:**
 - Summarises the main conclusions of the created guidelines and presents the limitations of the work conducted, as well as other aspects that need further investigation;
- **References**

2. Ecodesign parameters for SSB cell design

2.1 Current State of Art – SSB LCA, costs and ecodesign

In the literature, several LCA studies and approaches to ecodesign guidelines for batteries are found. In most of these studies, the focus is given to current market-level battery technologies, i.e., 3rd generation lithium-ion batteries (LIBs), which contain a liquid electrolyte. The scope of this work focuses on the 4th generation of LIBs (with a solid electrolyte), and due to its infancy, the environmental and economic studies on SSBs are more limited.

In this section, the main conclusions, strategies, and most important parameters to effectively reduce the environmental impact of LIBs and SSB were collected from the literature, and analysed to determine their potential applicability for developing eco-design guidelines for SSB. The literature search was conducted using scientific and academic databases, including ScienceDirect, Scopus, and Google Scholar. The search involved relevant keywords such as “life cycle assessment of solid-state batteries”, “design of solid-state batteries”, and “eco-design of solid-state batteries”. The search focused on publications of environmental impact assessment and battery design solutions for low environmental and economic impacts.

The literature on the LCA of LIBs (3rd generation) mainly concludes that focus should be given to the cathode and anode materials and cell design for impact mitigation. In Mogensen & Rousse⁴, a systematic ecodesign approach for LiFe(PO)₄ (LFP) LIBs was presented. Based on LCA studies on LIBs and ecodesign strategies for material and energy optimization that were available in the literature, the authors categorised several parameters according to their linkage to the overall environmental performance (direct or indirect). The identified main contributors to the life cycle impacts were the cathode, with 33 to 50% of impacts, due to the presence of Li salts and ethylene carbonate materials in its composition, followed by the anode (generally graphite) and the battery casing. Focusing on functionality requirements, the parameters of safety, energy density, lifespan, costs, and weight were the most important parameters identified by the study for optimal material and energy usage. This was also verified in Sanker et al¹¹ where a review of LCA results for the entire life cycle of LIBs was conducted. Here, the authors also determined that the main drivers of impacts during production are the cathode manufacturing and cell production. The authors mention that replacement of polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) binders by aqueous binders and increase use of hydrometallurgical processes for a closed-loop battery recycling process can greatly improve LIB environmental performance. It is important to note that there is a recent governmental proposal to limit the use of fluorinated polymers due to the potential release of “forever chemicals” (Per and poly-fluoroalkyl substances - PFAs) during manufacturing¹².

Zhang et al.¹³ also assessed the ecodesign parametrization for batteries, focusing on SSBs. In this study, the authors defined a simulation model for the environmental performance assessment of several battery designs for EV LIBs to support design decisions. The authors used a model of an EV battery pack based on

¹¹ Sankar, Tapan Kumar, Abhilash, and Pratima Meshram. 2024. “Environmental Impact Assessment in the Entire Life Cycle of Lithium-Ion Batteries.” *Reviews of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology* 262 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44169-023-00054-w>.

¹² Lohmann, Rainer, Ian T. Cousins, Jamie C. Dewitt, Juliane Glüge, Gretta Goldenman, Dorte Herzke, Andrew B. Lindstrom, et al. 2020. “Are Fluoropolymers Really of Low Concern for Human and Environmental Health and Separate from Other PFAS?” *Environmental Science and Technology* 54 (20): 12820–28. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.0c03244>.

¹³ Zhang, Cheng, Yun Liu, Yongming Qian, and Hong Bao. 2020. “An Optimization Framework of Electric Vehicle (EV) Batteries for Product Eco-Design.” *Procedia CIRP* 90: 366–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2020.01.081>.

a prismatic cell model in a stiff pouch, which was available in BatPaC¹⁴. Two optimized battery pack designs were determined to increase the driving range and reduce the environmental impacts. The optimal driving range had fewer modules and more cells in each model, increasing the amount of energy stored. The optimal environmental performance design had a higher cell thickness due to the increased thickness of the anode, along with more modules in the pack and fewer cells per module, leading to a lower pack weight and lower environmental impacts.

It is important to understand the main aspects that influence the environmental performance of SSBs in order to establish an ecodesign strategy capable of significantly reducing or mitigating the potential environmental impacts. However, due to the high variability of materials for the composition of SSBs and the low technology readiness level (TRL), the literature results vary greatly. Accardo et al.¹⁵ compared the potential environmental impact of future Li-ion battery technologies (SSB, Li-S, and new Si anodes: nanostructured and micro-structured) making use of prospective LCA (p-LCA), a new approach to determine the environmental performance of emerging technologies, considering the evolution of society, technology, economy and policies (Olsen et al.¹⁶). The p-LCA considered an SSB cell with a Li-M anode and a protective layer on the current collector made of silver nanoparticles. The results showed that the anode contributed to more than 58% of the total environmental impacts of the SSB cell due to the existing protective layer. This was also validated by Liu et al.¹⁷, where the SE and Li-M anode were the main contributors for the carbon footprint of the two SSB systems considered, and in Popien et al.¹⁸, where the NMC and NCA cathode alternatives have the highest contributions. Mandade et al.¹⁹ developed a framework for p-LCA of emerging SSBs, using current LCA studies of SSBs to assess each life cycle phase to support ecodesign decisions. Most of the existing literature on the LCA of SSB cells relies on inventory data from laboratory conditions, leading to high levels of uncertainty when attempting to extrapolate to upscaled levels of technological development. Furthermore, variations of results related to the selected functional unit, system boundaries and quantification methods make it difficult to extrapolate consensus regarding the total impacts of SSBs. The authors concluded that additional features related to the SSB can influence the environmental performance, such as the type of electrolyte, the TRL of the assessed process and the overall performance of the developed SSB cell. Nonetheless, the calculated impacts have a range

¹⁴ Knehr, Kevin W., Kubal, Joseph J., Nelson, Paul A., and Ahmed, Shabbir. 2022. "Battery Performance and Cost Modeling for Electric-Drive Vehicles (A Manual for BatPaC v5.0)". United States. <https://doi.org/10.2172/1877590>. <https://www.osti.gov/servlets/purl/1877590>.

¹⁵ Accardo, Antonella, Ambrogio Garofalo, Giovanni Dotelli, and Ezio Spessa. 2024. "Prospective LCA of Next-Generation Cells for Electric Vehicle Applications." *IEEE Access* 12 (January): 19584–97. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3361312>.

¹⁶ Olsen, Stig Irving, Mads Borup, and Per Dannemand Andersen. 2017. "Future-Oriented LCA." In *Life Cycle Assessment: Theory and Practice*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-56475-3_21.

¹⁷ Liu, Ziyi, Xi Li, Hongliang Zhang, Kai Huang, and Yajuan Yu. 2024. "Are Solid-State Batteries Absolutely More Environmentally Friendly Compared to Traditional Batteries-Analyzing from the Footprint Family Viewpoint." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 447 (November 2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.141452>.

¹⁸ Popien, Jan Linus, Christian Thies, Alexander Barke, and Thomas S. Spengler. 2023. "Comparative Sustainability Assessment of Lithium-Ion, Lithium-Sulfur, and All-Solid-State Traction Batteries." *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 28 (4): 462–77. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-023-02134-4>.

¹⁹ Mandade, Prasad, Marcel Weil, Manuel Baumann, and Zhixuan Wei. 2023. "Environmental Life Cycle Assessment of Emerging Solid-State Batteries: A Review." *Chemical Engineering Journal Advances* 13 (December 2022): 100439. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceja.2022.100439>.

higher than current LIBs (range of 0.1 to 18 kg CO₂ eq/Wh for SSB versus 0.025 to 0.35 kg CO₂ eq/Wh for current LIBs²⁰).

Troy et al.²¹ conducted an LCA of a laboratory-level SSB pouch cell to determine the main environmental hotspots and assess potential efficiency improvement actions and upscaling. The authors admitted that the low technological readiness level can showcase new technologies as having more environmental impacts than their fully developed counterparts. However, the obtained results can still be proven important when assessing potential action plans for improvement. Compared to lab-level processes, the upscaling of the SSB production can potentially reduce environmental impacts due to more efficient energy consumption. In addition to electricity consumption, optimising the thickness of the lithium metal anode can lead to substantial environmental impact reductions (50-98%). Resource analysis of the applied materials in the SSB cell also concluded that lithium, lanthanum and zirconium are highly critical materials that should be limited in the cell design. Schreiber et al.²² analysed lithium lanthanum zirconium oxide (LLZO) and lithium aluminium titanium phosphate (LATP) SSB cells in a laboratorial scale. Different synthesis methods were considered; however, the high uncertainty level of the obtained results did not allow to ascertain the best performing alternative between spray drying and solid-state reaction. The results indicated that the cathode materials, similarly to 3rd generation LIBs, are also the main contributors to the environmental impacts. The authors noted that the considered energy consumption during cell production may have been overestimated due to the lack of optimization in the laboratorial conditions (e.g., cell assembly in a glove box). The LATP material achieved the lowest environmental impacts, but improvements should be made to reduce its thickness. The authors also recommend the use of PVD or sol-gel thin film as separator to reduce the separator thickness. Here, the authors also mention the use of protective layers to improve cycling stability and the switch from NMC622 to NMC811 to reduce the cathode impacts.

Regarding potential mitigation actions to SSB design, Picatoste et al.²³ conducted a literature review of LCA studies on EV LIBs to identify and characterise circular strategies found in these studies and to provide guidelines regarding the best actions to improve the environmental performance of LIBs. Based on a common terminology to define and identify circular economy strategies (Blomsma et al.²⁴), the authors identified potential environmental savings through the reduction of battery weight, energy efficiency improvements during manufacturing and use, extend the battery lifetime and second-life applications, and

²⁰ Peters, Jens F., Manuel Baumann, Benedikt Zimmermann, Jessica Braun, and Marcel Weil. 2017. "The Environmental Impact of Li-Ion Batteries and the Role of Key Parameters – A Review." *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 67: 491–506. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.08.039>.

²¹ Troy, Stefanie, Andrea Schreiber, Thorsten Reppert, Hans Gregor Gehrke, Martin Finsterbusch, Sven Uhlenbruck, and Peter Stenzel. 2016. "Life Cycle Assessment and Resource Analysis of All-Solid-State Batteries." *Applied Energy* 169: 757–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.02.064>.

²² Schreiber, Andrea, Melanie Rosen, Katja Waetzig, Kristian Nikolowski, Nikolas Schiffmann, Hartmut Wiggers, Michael Küpers, et al. 2022. "Oxide Ceramic Electrolytes for All-Solid-State Lithium Batteries - Cost-Cutting Cell Design and Environmental Impact." *Green Chemistry* 25 (1): 399–414. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2gc03368b>.

²³ Picatoste, Aitor, Daniel Justel, and Joan Manuel F. Mendoza. 2022. "Circularity and Life Cycle Environmental Impact Assessment of Batteries for Electric Vehicles: Industrial Challenges, Best Practices and Research Guidelines." *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 169 (112941): 15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112941>.

²⁴ Blomsma, Fenna, Marina Pieroni, Mariia Kravchenko, Daniela C.A. Pigosso, Jutta Hildenbrand, Anna Rùna Kristinsdottir, Eivind Kristoffersen, et al. 2019. "Developing a Circular Strategies Framework for Manufacturing Companies to Support Circular Economy-Oriented Innovation." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 241. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118271>.

optimisation of standard battery recycling processes, with NMC as the most interesting chemistry for repurposing and recycling due to their high energy density and the presence of CRM such as cobalt that can be recovered.

CRMs were also mentioned as a crucial point in reducing the environmental impacts of SSBs in other studies (Accardo et al.¹⁵, Kononova et al.²⁵). Accardo et al.¹⁵ concluded that eliminating silver compounds for material synthesis would make the SSB chemistry the best-performing alternative from the analyzed potential chemistries of future LIBs. The authors stated that the presence of CRM hinders the sustainability of LIBs, where the main challenge for SSB technology lies in developing deposition processes for the lithium anode and optimizing the solid electrolytes' ionic conductivity. The concern for the circularity of high-value materials and CRMs present in SSB was also assessed by Kononova et al.²⁵, who established a process to define the target materials for SSB recycling, considering polymer, oxide and sulphide electrolytes to support SSB design for recycling. Using the Sherwood approach, the authors identified the materials that should be the focus of the SSB recycling process, considering environmental and economic aspects and supply risks. Taking into account circularity parameters, recycling efficiency and the quality of recycled materials, the authors emphasise that although the CRM of SSB can be recovered through recycling, the reactivity of Li anode and sulphide-based SSBs can be challenging to safely handle and recycle. Nonetheless, the study concluded that the economic and environmental benefits of recycling activities can be potentiated through the recovery of Li, Ta, Co, Ni, Al and Cu, as well as LLZO as a component (e.g., through direct recycling).

Recycling is an important phase for the environmental performance of SSBs, as is when there is an opportunity to recover and extend the lifetime of CRM and components and potentiate their integration into the battery value chain, where they have high economic value. In Tan et al.²⁶, new recycling strategies for successfully handling the new SSB batteries were presented. The Everbatt model²⁷ was employed by the authors to compare the developed recycling strategies with conventional recycling processes (pyro and hydrometallurgy). Direct recycling methods allow for the reduction of the environmental impacts of the recycling process. The recycling strategy involved an initial removal of the battery casing and immersion of the cell stack into a solution processing (e.g., ethanol, acetonitrile) for sulphide-based solid-state electrolytes (SE). Then, the dissolved SE and the precipitated cathode material are separated through filtration or gravity-based separation methods. The solvent is dried to recover the electrolyte and cathode materials and send them for regeneration (e.g., through thermal annealing and chemical re-lithiation). The authors also determined that recovering the electrolyte generated a small increase in energy consumption and environmental impacts. The regeneration of the obtained materials into new cells with similar performances allowed the validation of the process.

²⁵ Kononova, Nelli, Steffen Blömeke, Felipe Cerdas, Sabrina Zellmer, and Christoph Herrmann. 2023. "Identification of Target Materials for Recycling of Solid-State Batteries from Environmental and Economic Perspective Using Information Theory Entropy." *Procedia CIRP* 116: 185–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2023.02.032>.

²⁶ Tan, Darren H.S., Panpan Xu, Hedi Yang, Min cheol Kim, Han Nguyen, Erik A. Wu, Jean Marie Doux, Abhik Banerjee, Ying Shirley Meng, and Zheng Chen. 2020. "Sustainable Design of Fully Recyclable All Solid-State Batteries." *MRS Energy and Sustainability* 7 (1): 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1557/mre.2020.25>.

²⁷ Argonne National Laboratory. 2019. "EverBatt: Argonne's Closed-Loop Battery Life-Cycle Model - Accelerating the Advancement of Battery Life-Cycle Solutions," 5543. https://www.anl.gov/sites/www/files/2019-02/EGS_EverBatt_fact-sheet-2019.pdf.

The current literature on LCA for SSB is limited due to the lack of primary information on the production processes and the processing of materials that are not part of the currently used lithium-ion batteries.

For example, the lithium-metal (Li-M) anode (currently being considered for the ADVAGEN cell) requires a protective layer made from other elements, and the SE, is currently under study for optimized composition with a variety of potential materials, and optimized production (e.g., digitally-supported production processes¹). In addition, the environmental impacts during the use phase are still based on assumptions as the SSB has not yet been rolled out to the electric vehicle market. In addition, recycling impacts are estimated based on standard recycling processes and do not consider new upcoming automated dismantling processes for more efficient recycling, nor the new materials incorporated into SSBs that are of high value. As such, the several variables to be considered for a proper environmental performance assessment of SSBs make it difficult to determine the best pathway forward. Nonetheless, more recent literature has tackled these challenges in order to support design decisions that are in line with better-performing SSB systems regarding functionality, safety and sustainability.

Regarding cost reduction, technical reports^{28,29} have mentioned that increasing cell size can support cost and environmental impact mitigation due to the corresponding energy consumption and equipment usage. Other strategies are related to the drying process, by decreasing the solvent amount or the use of other solvent materials. Costs are also an important factor when assessing the usage of critical materials (e.g., germanium), especially in the SE, as these materials are considered a risk factor to ensure lower and stable market cost³⁰. Digitalisation for production system design and monitoring considering key parameters can also support cost and waste reduction³¹. Finally, increasing the recycling of SSBs is heavily dependent on the revenue obtained from the recovery of high-value materials present in the battery system (e.g., lithium salts, SE materials and cathode active materials (CAM))^{11,25}.

From the gathered literature, it is possible to ascertain that the key takeaways to consider for ecodesign strategies when it comes to improving environmental performance are:

²⁸ Hettesheimer, Tim, Christoph Neef, Inés Rosellón Inclán, Steffen Link, Thomas Schmaltz, Felix Schuckert, Annegret Stephan, et al. 2023. "Lithium-Ion Battery Roadmap – Industrialization Perspectives Toward 2030." Fraunhofer ISI, no. December: 10.24406/publica-2153.

²⁹ Heimes, Heiner, Achim Kampker, Sarah Wennemar, Lorenz Plocher, Gerrit Bockey, Sarah Michaelis, and Jörg Schruppf. 2019. "Production Process of a Lithium-Ion Battery Cell." Aachen. https://www.pem.rwth-aachen.de/global/show_document.asp?id=aaaaaaaabyilawq.

³⁰ Janek, Jürgen, and Wolfgang G Zeier. 2023. "Challenges in Speeding up Solid-State Battery Development." *Nature Energy* 8 (3): 230–40. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-023-01208-9>.

³¹ Buck, Felix, Christoph Imdahl, Nikolas Dilger, Sabrina Zellmer, and Christoph Herrmann. 2023. "Simulation-Based Planning of Process Chains and Production Environments for Solid-State Batteries." *Procedia CIRP* 116: 426–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2023.02.072>.

Reduction of CRM in the SSB

Special focus on lithium, lanthanum, zirconium, germanium and silver

Increase the recycling efficiency

Of high-value materials and CRM, especially for NMC cathodes

Recyclable SSB design

For direct recycling methods: focus on the SE and cell active materials

Increase energy and material efficiency

During manufacturing and use

Reduction of battery weight

Per capacity

Increase battery lifetime

Including energy density & size

Optimisation of the thickness

Of cell components

Promote second-life applications

Reduce costs

Especially during production

2.2 Regulatory Trends towards sustainable European batteries

Europe has made significant commitments towards sustainability, especially towards climate neutrality by 2050. Transport is one of the main areas to tackle concerning the greenhouse emissions mitigation. Betting on the electrification of the transport sector, Europe has been focusing on shifting from the use of fossil fuels to batteries for vehicles. Batteries play an important role as a mobile device of electric energy storage, serving as a key element for sustainable development, promoting green mobility, facilitating the adoption of clean energy, and advancing efforts towards achieving climate neutrality³².

To ensure that the Union's product policies contribute to reducing global carbon emissions, it's essential that products available in the Union are sourced and manufactured sustainably. This ensures that the environmental impact of products sold and marketed within the Union is minimized, contributing to broader efforts to combat climate change worldwide.

Ecodesign directive

In its ongoing pursuit of sustainable product manufacturing, the European Union established a framework for the design of more sustainable products with Directive 2009/125/EC⁷, later superseded by the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR)¹⁰. The ecodesign Directive 2009/125/EC aims to encourage the design of products with a reduced environmental impact throughout their life cycle by promoting the use of fewer resources and less energy during production, use, and disposal. This framework covers a wide range of energy-related products (ErPs), which includes products that use, generate, transfer, or measure energy, as well as products with significant energy-saving potential during use. The New Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation enters into force on the 18th of July¹⁰. Such regulation establishes a framework for setting ecodesign requirements for sustainable products and repealing Directive 2009/125/EC, which sets out specific requirements that products must meet to be sold within the European Union:

- **Energy efficiency:** Products must meet a certain level of energy efficiency to be placed on the EU market.
- **Resource Efficiency:** Promotes the use of materials that are sustainable and have a lower environmental impact. This includes using recycled materials and designing products that are easier to disassemble for recycling.
- **Material restrictions:** Certain harmful materials might be banned or limited in products.
- **Design for Longevity and Durability:** Encourages designing products for longer lifespan, repairable, and maintainable. This reduces the need for frequent replacements, thus conserving resources
- **End-of-Life Management:** Requires that products be designed to facilitate reuse, dismantling, and recycling. This helps in managing waste and promoting a circular economy.
- **Information requirements:** Manufacturers must provide information on the environmental performance of their products. This includes labelling, technical documentation, and instructions for efficient use and proper disposal.
- **Standardized labelling:** Labels might be required to communicate a product's environmental performance to consumers.

³² European Commission. 2020. "Horizon Europe." 2020. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe_en.

Obligations for stakeholders:

Manufacturers

Manufacturers must ensure their products comply with the ecodesign requirements for the relevant product group. This might involve redesigning products, using different materials, or providing additional information to consumers.

Importers

They are responsible for ensuring that the products they import into the EU comply with ecodesign requirements.

Retailers

They may have obligations to provide information to consumers about the environmental performance of products they sell.

For the conception of a product, this directive considers the parameters presented in Table 1.

Table 1 - Parameters from the proposal for the new ecodesign Regulation.

Design Parameter	Description
Durability and reliability of the product or its components	Guaranteed product lifespan, technical lifespan, average time between failures, real-use information on the product, and resistance to stress or aging mechanisms.
Ease of repair and maintenance	Characteristics, availability and delivery time of spare parts, modularity, compatibility with commonly available spare parts, availability of repair and maintenance instructions, number of materials and components used, use of standard components, use of component and material coding standards for the identification of components and materials, number and complexity of processes and tools needed, ease of non-destructive disassembly and re-assembly, conditions for access to product data, conditions for access to or use of hardware and software needed.
Ease of upgrading, re-use, remanufacturing and refurbishment	Number of materials and components used, use of standard components, use of component and material coding standards for the identification of components and materials, number and complexity of processes and tools needed, ease of non-destructive disassembly and re-assembly, conditions for access to product data, conditions for access to or use of hardware and software needed, conditions of access to test protocols or not commonly available testing equipment, availability of guarantees specific to remanufactured or refurbished products, conditions for access to or use of technologies protected by intellectual property rights, modularity.
Ease and quality of recycling	Use of easily recyclable materials, safe, easy and non-destructive access to recyclable components and materials or components and materials containing hazardous substances, material composition and homogeneity, possibility for high-purity sorting, number of materials and components used, use of standard components, use of component and material coding standards for the identification of components and materials, number and complexity of processes and tools needed, ease of non-destructive disassembly and re-

Design Parameter	Description
Avoidance of technical solutions detrimental	Assembly, conditions for access to product data, conditions for access to or use of hardware and software needed.
	Re-use, upgrade, repair, conduct maintenance, refurbish, remanufacture and recycle products and components.
Use of substances	Use of substances, on their own, as constituents of substances or in mixtures, during the production process of products, or leading to their presence in products, including once these products become waste.
Consumption of energy, water and other resources	Consumption of resources in one or more life cycle stages of the product, including the effect of physical factors or software and firmware updates on product efficiency and the impact on deforestation.
Use or content of recycled materials	Incorporation of recycled content into product manufacturing
Weight and volume	Weight and volume of the product and its packaging, and the product-to-packaging ratio.
Incorporation of used components	Incorporation of used components into product manufacturing.
Consumables for maintenance	Quantity, characteristics and availability of consumables needed for proper use and maintenance.
The environmental footprint and carbon footprint	Quantification, in accordance with the applicable delegated act, of a product's life cycle environmental impacts, whether in relation to one or more environmental impact categories or an aggregated set of impact categories.
Emissions to air, water or soil	Released in one or more life cycle stages of the product.
Waste generated	Amounts of waste generated.

The parameters presented aim to support the conception of more sustainable products, by minimizing the product's environmental impacts through resource efficiency, waste reduction, and life cycle extension for both the product itself and its constituent parts.

Concerning the ESPR, it doesn't set specific requirements itself, instead, it provides a framework for developing product-specific regulations.

Each regulated product group has its own "implementing act", at the moment, the EU is creating and implementing acts for new product groups and revising the old ones. The new acts aren't yet into force. However, once the ESPR is enacted, it will assume control of these acts and replace the existing Ecodesign Directive. Concerning batteries, there isn't any category group created yet.

The ESPR introduces the concept of a Digital Product Passport (DPP) for products. This DPP will provide an accessible digital label containing information, such as: durability, reparability, the recycled content or the availability of spare parts of a product. This information will be available to everyone involved in the product's life cycle, from manufacturers and regulators to consumers.

This framework will apply to all products sold within the EU market, regardless of their origin. It will be in line with the international trade regulations. Additionally, the European Commission will actively collaborate and partner with producing countries that aim to improve product sustainability.

From both these documents, dominant topics were identified, such as Resource efficiency, Recycling content and efficiency, Product Performance, Durability, Waste Logistics, Second-life potential, Environmental Impact, Emissions and waste generation. Besides the fact that these documents

complement each other, there are still gaps that need to be covered in terms of defining recommendations and targets regarding:

- Material selection
- Recycling requirements
- Safety measures for transport
- First life extension
- Second life
- Battery directive too generic to address all different types of batteries

Exploring these topics will contribute to a more robust and complete conception of more sustainable products.

Overall, both of these political regulations play an important role on the development of sustainable technologies by providing a foundation with mandatory ecological requirements. Ensuring that products are designed with their entire life cycle in mind, promoting energy efficiency, resource conservation, and waste reduction. It's important for interactive international cooperation to promote fair trade and minimise unnecessary burdens on third-world countries, as most of them are part of the battery supply chain.

Battery Regulation

In recognition of this growing need for sustainable battery solutions, Europe has undertaken a comprehensive approach. A suite of policies, directives, and initiatives have been established to foster the development, production, and use of batteries that prioritise environmental responsibility, economic competitiveness, and social well-being. A prime example of this commitment is the recent implementation of the new Battery Regulation (entered into force 17 August 2023)⁶.

The battery regulation is a legal framework to guarantee that upcoming batteries possess a reduced environmental footprint, minimize the use of detrimental substances, require fewer raw materials sourced from non-EU nations, and undergo extensive collection, reutilization, and recycling processes within Europe. This initiative aims to sustain the transition towards clean energy and a circular economy, improve the security of raw materials and energy supplies, and strengthen the EU's strategic independence.

In this regard, requirements are established concerning sustainability, safety, waste management, performance, durability, labelling, and information.

Regarding sustainability and safety concerns, the topics being considered are the following:

- **Restriction on substances** - The European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) will prepare a report focusing on substances that pose significant risks to human health and the environment, and can compromise the safe and efficient recycling of materials, preventing them from being transformed into valuable, high-quality secondary raw materials;
- **Carbon footprint (CF)** – efforts related to the harmonization of the technical rules for the CF calculation harmonized introduction of CF declaration and consequent establishment of CF performance classes are made. There are already target deadlines to enter into force either of the delegated act or of the implementing act, respectively, or 12 months after it, as presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - Main battery carbon footprint timeline for EV batteries.

- Recycling content** – Batteries that contain cobalt, lead, lithium or nickel will be required to achieve specific recycling content targets, presented in Figure 3. Both production waste and post-consumer waste are valid sources, and the targets must be achieved for each battery model, per production plant and per production year.

Figure 3 - Recycling contents percentages share to be achieved, per battery model, per year and per manufacturing plant.

A methodology for the calculation and verification of these percentages will be developed by 16 August 2026, alongside a target reassessment no later than 31 December 2028.

- Performance and durability requirements** – Electrochemical and durability parameters were established in Part A of Annex IV, regarding minimum values of their performance. Table 2 presents the requirements related to the performance and durability.

Table 2 - Performance and durability requirements.

Part A – Parameters related to electrochemical performance and durability	Part B – Elements to explain the measurements for parameters
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rated capacity (in Ah) and capacity fade (%) Power (W) and power fade (%) Internal resistance (Ω) and internal resistance (%) Where applicable, energy round trip efficiency (%) and its fade (%) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Applied discharge rate and charge rate Ratio between nominal battery power (W) and battery energy (Wh) Depth of discharge in the cycle-life test Power capability at 80% and 20% state of charge (SoC)

Part A – Parameters related to electrochemical performance and durability	Part B – Elements to explain the measurements for parameters
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expected lifetime of the battery under the reference conditions for which it has been designed in terms of cycles, except for non-cycle applications, and calendar years. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Any calculations performed with the measured parameters, if applicable

Labelling and information focuses on ensuring clear and consistent information is available to consumers and stakeholders throughout the battery lifecycle. Batteries will require mandatory labelling with clear, up-to-date and accurate information. This implies information related to the battery capacity, indication of rechargeable or non-rechargeable nature, chemical composition, Recycling symbols, QR code linking to a more comprehensive information database. This labelling system aims to improve consumer awareness about battery characteristics, proper use, and responsible disposal practices. Additionally, the information will facilitate battery identification and sorting for efficient recycling.

One of the main innovations that will be implemented for the battery product is the **DPP for batteries**, that will be made available through a QR code and provide detailed information on each battery individually to support stakeholders along the value chain for use, disassembly and recycling. The battery passport will support decision making in each of these life cycle stages through the characterization of the battery design, chemistry, existing CRM in each battery component, their amounts, manufacturing location, suppliers, and more.

Management of waste batteries focuses on the collection and recycling of waste batteries at their end-of-life. Economic operators responsible for placing batteries on the market shall have extended producer responsibility for batteries that they make available on the market for the first time, even economic operators that make available on the market for the first time a battery that results from preparation for re-use and repurposing, repurposing or remanufacturing operations. This means producers bear significant financial and organizational responsibility for the collection, treatment, and recycling of their waste batteries. Additionally, economic operators involved in waste battery management are required to report data on the types and quantities of batteries collected and recycled.

The targets for recycling efficiency and material recovery are presented in Figure 4. This ensures that valuable materials are recovered at a high rate and reused in new battery production.

Figure 4 - Timeline for new targets regarding material recovery rates.

The Commission is expected to define a methodology for calculating and verifying recycling efficiency and material recovery rates. This methodology will be established by February 18, 2025.

In summary, for EV batteries, requirements are established concerning sustainability and safety, waste management, performance, durability, labelling, and information. These requirements are essential for authorizing their introduction into the market or utilization within the EU. This encompasses a mandate to disclose and denote the carbon footprint of the battery, alongside the implementation of a digital passport. Objectives for the collection and treatment of waste batteries are set and outlines specifications for information and reporting.

From this document, the most relevant parameters for battery design are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 - Parameters per topic from the battery regulation

PARAMETERS PER TOPIC FROM THE BATTERY REGULATION			
SUSTAINABILITY AND SAFETY	PERFORMANCE AND DURABILITY	LABELLING AND INFORMATION REQUIREMENTS	END-OF-LIFE MANAGEMENT
Restrictions on substances	Minimum performance criteria (capacity and energy efficiency)	Battery performance, durability, material content, and recycling (battery passport, QR Code)	Recycling efficiency targets
Carbon Footprint of EV batteries	Minimum life cycle (Expected lifetime of the battery)	-	Recovery of materials (Co, Cu, Pb, Li, Ni)
Recycled content	-	-	-
Supply Chain Transparency	-	-	-

2.3 Other regulatory market strategies

Europe recognizes how constantly and fast world changes and acknowledges how important it is to be prepared in forecasting and mitigating the negative impacts. In this regard, Europe has been paying attention in key areas: supply chain security, technological innovation, economic competitiveness, environmental sustainability. Following this, Europe has been developing regulations and policies to support Europe's sustainable development. Besides the Battery Regulation and the Ecodesign Directive, Europe deployed other legislative instruments, as for example:

- The **Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA)** is an initiative by the European Union with focus to secure a sustainable and resilient supply of **Critical Raw Materials (CRM)** essential for the EU's green and digital transitions³³. These materials are crucial for the production of various high-tech and clean energy applications, as: batteries, electric vehicles, renewable energy technologies, and electronics. This initiative aims to reduce the dependence of CRM and encourages partnerships with non-EU countries to ensure a stable and secure supply chain. This Act lists the strategic raw materials for the EU, where the following are used in batteries: Lithium, Manganese, Graphite and Nickel.

In this legislative instrument, several requirements are identified that can also be applied to the battery product and are in line with the parameters identified in the current ecodesign directive, such as:

- Durability;
- Reusability;
- Resource use or resource efficiency;
- Possibility of remanufacturing and recycling;
- Recycled content;
- Possibility of recovery of materials.

Additionally, the CRMA also sets targets concerning the EU's annual consumption of CRM as a measure to increase EU's independence to achieve by 2030:

- At least **10%** must come from EU **extraction**;
- At least **40%** must come from EU **processing**;
- At least **15%** must come from EU **recycling**;
- No more than 65% **comes from a single third country**.

- The **Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP)** is a plan that aims to promote the transition towards a more circular and sustainable economy. It promotes the sustainability of product/services/business models, the reduction of waste, recycling, and promote sustainable consumption and production patterns.³⁴

³³ Office of the European Union L-, Publications, and Luxembourg Luxembourg. n.d. "Regulation (EU) 2024/1252 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 April 2024 Establishing a Framework for Ensuring a Secure and Sustainable Supply of Critical Raw Materials and Amending Regulations (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1724 and (EU) 2019/1020Text with EEA Relevance." <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1252/oj>.

³⁴ European Commission. 2020. "A New Circular Economy Action Plan." <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sustainable-consumption-production/>.

- **Waste Framework Directive (WFD)** is an instrument that aims to support the sustainable waste management and ensure the human health and environment protection. This directive encourages the prevention and reduction of waste generation, recycling and recovery.³⁵
- The **REACH Regulation** (Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals) focus on the safe handling of chemicals within the EU by restricting or banning certain hazardous substances. This is something that can influence battery manufacturing, pushing manufacturers towards safer and more sustainable alternatives. This regulation aims to protect human health and the environment by requiring manufacturers and importers to register and provide detailed information about the chemicals they produce or import.³⁶

Other trends around the world:

A global trend towards sustainable battery production and recycling is gaining momentum, reflected in the development of regulations and policies worldwide. Regarding the main battery manufacturers in the world, it is observed the following:

United States of America:

- **The Inflation Reduction Act (IRA):** This act focuses on clean energy and climate change, aiming to reduce greenhouse emissions and to strengthen the supply chain resilience. It encourages domestic manufacturing, research and innovation, use of renewable energy, and recycling initiatives through funding programs^{37,38,39}

China:

- **14th Five-Year Plan for the Development of the Raw Materials Industry:** focus on resource security, technological innovation, green development, industrial modernization, and supply chain resilience. China seeks to ensure a stable supply of critical raw materials necessary for its economic growth and technological advancement.
- **The Lithium-ion Battery Industry Specification Conditions:** is a set of guidelines and regulations that covers the Li-ion batteries industry, they focus on regulating the production, quality, safety and environmental impact.

³⁵ European Parliament. 2008. "Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on Waste and Repealing Certain Directives." Official Journal of European Union L312: 1–59. <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2008:312:0003:01:ES:HTML>.

³⁶ European Parliament. 2022. "Of the European Parliament and of the Council." https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/chemicals/reach-regulation_en.

³⁷ US Department of the Treasury. n.d. "Inflation Reduction Act." Accessed May 5, 2024. <https://home.treasury.gov/policy-issues/inflation-reduction-act>.

³⁸ U.S. Department of Energy. n.d. "Inflation Reduction Act of 2022." Accessed May 5, 2024. <https://www.energy.gov/lpo/inflation-reduction-act-2022>.

³⁹ Minespider. 2022. "EV Battery Regulations around the World: What You Need to Know." 2022. <https://www.minespider.com/blog/ev-battery-regulations-around-the-world-what-you-need-to-know>.

- **Interim Measures for the Management of Recycling and Utilisation of New Energy Power Vehicle Battery:** are regulating frameworks that address the growing need for effective recycling and utilization of batteries for new energy vehicles. These regulations focus on responsibility (manufacturers, automakers, and recycling companies), encourage recycling and resource recovery, emphasize safety and environmental protection throughout the process, traceability, and data sharing.^{40,41}
- **Interim Provisions on the Management of Traceability of Recycling and Utilisation of New Energy Vehicles Power Battery:** is regulatory framework designed to enhance the traceability and management of the lifecycle of batteries used in new energy vehicles. These provisions aim to ensure that batteries are effectively recycled and utilized, minimizing environmental impact.⁴²
- **Guidelines for Construction and Operation of New Energy Vehicle Power Battery Recycling Service Outlets:** These guidelines provide standardized guidelines for collection and management of used batteries from new energy vehicles, aiming for proper handling and promoting sustainable recycling.

Despite each region having its own regulatory frameworks and policies, they converge on fundamental principles. These countries recognize the imperative pursuit for the sustainable development. They are investing significantly in innovation and R&D, emphasizing the importance of responsible and resilient supply chains and concerned with environmental impacts. The U.S. and Europe are actively investing in creating their own domestic battery production capabilities to lessen dependence on external sources⁴³.

In the context of batteries, efforts are being made: to establish sustainable manufacturing processes, to implement responsible management of EoL batteries, to achieve efficient recycling and recovery of materials, and to ensure accessible digital data and labelling, there is a global consensus towards sustainable battery management practices in these different regions. These regions are making efforts to create regulations and policies for more sustainable products and systems by developing funding programs to achieve their common goals.

⁴⁰ Auto Recycling World. 2023. "China Set to Strengthen EV Battery Recycling Regulation: Upgrades and Enhancements Planned." 2023. <https://autorecyclingworld.com/china-set-to-strengthen-ev-battery-recycling-regulation-upgrades-and-enhancements-planned/>.

⁴¹ Beckett, Nick. n.d. "MIIT Issues the Interim Measures for the Management of Recycling and Utilisation of Power Batteries of New Energy Vehicles." <https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=9fe71d98-3aa6-4dec-bc3d-fef272367deb>.

⁴² SMM. 2018. "Ministry of Industry and Information Technology: New Energy Vehicle Power Battery Recycling Will Be Temporarily Traced Back to Source Management from August 1." 2018.

⁴³ Zhu, Nolan. 2024. "China Plans to Strengthen Lithium Battery Industry Regulations." 2024. <https://www.jurist.org/news/2024/05/china-plans-to-strengthen-lithium-battery-industry-regulations/>.

2.4 Ecodesign parameter identification

To identify the most pertinent parameters for the ecodesign of SBBs, an extensive literature research was undertaken, together with an examination of the current regulatory trends, including key legislative documents such as the battery regulation, the Ecodesign Directive and CRMA.

It was observed that these legislative instruments and literature had in common many of the topics and share the same concerns. The predominant topics approached were related to the: resource efficiency (materials, water and energy), recycling content and efficiency, durability, second-life, environmental impact, emissions and waste generation, labelling, and information requirements. In Table 4 are listed the relevant parameters identified in the different legislative initiatives and in the analysed SoA. Additionally, it is possible to observe the similar parameters between scientific literature and legislative documentation.

Table 4 - List of relevant parameters for SBBs ecodesign based on the conducted research analysis.

Parameter	Battery regulation	Ecodesign directive	Literature	CRMA
Resource efficiency	x	x	x	x
Restrictions on substances	x			
Carbon Footprint	x	x		
Environmental Footprint	x	x		
Recycled content	x	x	x	x
Supply chain transparency	x			
Technical Performance	x	x	x	
Recycling efficiency	x	x	x	x
Recovery of materials	x	x	x	
Durability	x	x	x	x
Ease of 2 nd life ⁴⁴		x	x	x
Avoidance of technical detrimental solutions		x		
Use of 2 nd hand materials		x		
Weight and volume		x	x	
Emissions and waste to air, water and soil		x		
Reduction of CRM			x	
Reduce costs			x	

From the conducted assessment, it was concluded that the previous battery directive is not specific enough to address the characteristics of electric vehicle (EV) batteries. Therefore, most of the identified design parameters were based on the Battery Regulation, the Ecodesign directive and the proposal for the new Ecodesign Regulation, which in turn was also very broad to conform with all energy-related products. Based on these documents and the previous literature analysis, several design parameters were defined as the most relevant for battery design:

- Resource efficiency (during production and in the end-of-life)
- Safety (Restrictions on substances)
- Carbon Footprint
- Environmental Footprint

⁴⁴ Ease of second life includes: repair, maintenance, upgrading, re-use, remanufacturing and refurbishment

- Recycled content
- Supply chain transparency
- Technical Performance
- Recycling efficiency
- Recovery of materials
- Durability
- Potential for second-life use (repurposing, remanufacturing, re-use and refurbishment)
- Use of second-life and recycled materials
- Weight and volume
- Emissions and waste to air, water and soil
- Reduction of CRM
- Reduce costs (material acquisition, production costs, logistics, etc.)

3. ADVAGEN battery expert design recommendations

The ADVAGEN consortium is represented by several research and industrial entities that play an active role in the battery value chain. The activities developed by partners allow them to have a unique perspective of the main technical and market challenges that LIBs are currently facing and that SSB will also face to become more sustainable. Several meetings were conducted with partners, complemented with individual interviews, to discuss the practical implementation of the identified ecodesign parameters into the ADVAGEN cell and identify the main difficulties, as well as potential solutions that, although could not be implemented currently in the project due to time constraints or due to the need of more technical R&D, may be applicable in the future. **This section presents the challenges and recommendations from ADVAGEN key battery experts to implement the previously defined ecodesign parameters in the ADVAGEN SSB cell.** The recommendations were sectioned according to their potential effects on the performance of the SSB cell in each of its life cycle stages (extraction, production, use, maintenance and end-of-life).

3.1 Challenges and recommendations for SSB ecodesign

3.1.1. Cell ecodesign for materials, manufacturing and assembly

When selecting the **cathode** chemistry, it is necessary to consider the best technical performing alternatives and conduct design decisions that allow for lower cost and environmental impact. These considerations must be analysed based on the battery capacity, which aligns with the functional unit selected in the new Battery Regulation⁶. In the context of the ADVAGEN project, the NMC cathode active material was selected due to its **high capacity, energy density, and longevity**, as well as easy upscaling^{45,46}.

When considering the cost risks associated with cobalt (due to supply risks from politically unstable sources⁴⁷) and the environmental and social impacts⁴⁸ of using this material, which is related to armed conflict, child labour and poor safety measures that generate health concerns and environmental contamination of water and land^{47,49}, the chemistry NMC811 was selected, which allows to **minimize the amount of cobalt**. This is also in line with the **target goals of the CRM Act**³³, specifically the limitation regarding the supply of CRM to no more than 65% coming from a single third country since at least 63%

⁴⁵ Saaid, Farish Irfal, Muhd Firdaus Kasim, Tan Winie, Kelimah Anak Elong, Azira Azahidi, Nurul Dhabitah Basri, Muhamad Kamil Yaakob, et al. 2024. "Ni-Rich Lithium Nickel Manganese Cobalt Oxide Cathode Materials: A Review on the Synthesis Methods and Their Electrochemical Performances." *Heliyon* 10 (1): e23968. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e23968>.

⁴⁶ Kwon, Yongbeom, Asya Svirinovsky-Arbeli, Julia C Hestenes, Pablo J Buitrago Botero, Kaitlin Rae M Corpus, Piotr Lepucki, Oliver Pecher, and Lauren E Marbella. 2024. "Elucidating the Role of Cathode Identity: Voltage-Dependent Reversibility of Anode-Free Batteries." *Chem*.

⁴⁷ Sovacool, Benjamin K. 2019. "The Precarious Political Economy of Cobalt: Balancing Prosperity, Poverty, and Brutality in Artisanal and Industrial Mining in the Democratic Republic of the Congo." *Extractive Industries and Society* 6 (3): 915–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.exis.2019.05.018>.

⁴⁸ Wesselkämper, Jannis, Laureen Dahrendorf, Lukas Mauler, Simon Lux, and Stephan von Delft. 2024. "Towards Circular Battery Supply Chains: Strategies to Reduce Material Demand and the Impact on Mining and Recycling." *Resources Policy* 95 (June). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2024.105160>.

⁴⁹ Niri, Anahita Jannesar, Gregory A. Poelzer, Steven E. Zhang, Jan Rosenkranz, Maria Pettersson, and Yousef Ghorbani. 2024. "Sustainability Challenges throughout the Electric Vehicle Battery Value Chain." *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 191 (December 2023): 114176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.114176>.

of global cobalt supply comes from the Democratic Republic of Congo, and 80% of cobalt refining occurs in China^{48,50,51}.

In addition, to produce battery-grade materials using secondary sources to achieve the 15% target for consuming recycled CRM from the CRM Act and the 16% Co, 6% Li, 6% Ni recycled materials incorporated in batteries in 2031 by the EU Battery Regulation, it is necessary to have water-soluble materials (i.e., the elements in salt form and, preferably, as nitrates) for a seamless integration. One of the current market challenges that manufacturers face is the low availability of these materials in the required format and purity level to produce and incorporate these secondary materials into batteries, and SSBs are not an exception. As such, it is recommended to establish key points between battery recycling stakeholders and manufacturers to allow for the recircularization of these materials back to the battery value chain. The ideal would be for raw materials producers to include recycled materials at the ore refining stage, so the cathode materials producers can buy raw materials that already fulfil the demands for recycled materials.

Nonetheless, the production process of NMC811 can be further optimized. Future SSB design is expected to have coatings or dopants in the cathode to increase structural stability and limit surface reactions^{52,53} between the positive electrode and the electrolyte, for e.g., Nb, Al, Fe, Mg/Zr, and Li_3PO_4 ^{45,54}. The cathode production must be optimized for **minimum amount and variety of CRM incorporated, and include secondary sources from battery recycling**. Since cathode manufacturing is the main contributor to the total production costs and environmental impacts, it is important to implement improvement actions to provide **meaningful cost and environmental impact mitigations**. Therefore, it is relevant to optimize and standardise the production process of NMC811 for an upscaled, streamlined production process. Based on this optimised process design, **digital monitoring tools** can ensure continuous optimal production efficiency, allowing for the **reduction of energy consumption and waste generation** (the more optimised the process is, the more predictable it can be to avoid defects), especially during slurry production and coating through **economy of scale**. For example, in dry room conditions, there is an ongoing energy consumption to ensure safety and product quality, and the development of air-to-air systems can help to **reduce energy consumption**, as well as the further development of water-based solvents instead of N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) for cathode coating. Wet processing for the cathode and solvent removal can also be beneficial, as it is already well established in battery and other industries and no change of equipment is necessary. Nonetheless, the choice on sulphide SE makes water-based coating out of the scope for the ADVAGEN cell.

⁵⁰ European Commission. 2023. "Study on the Critical Raw Materials for the EU." <https://doi.org/10.2873/725585>.

⁵¹ U.S. Geological Survey. 2024. "Mineral Commodity Summaries 2024: U.S. Geological Survey." <https://doi.org/10.3133/mcs2024>.

⁵² Britala, Liga, Mario Marinaro, and Gints Kucinskis. 2023. "A Review of the Degradation Mechanisms of NCM Cathodes and Corresponding Mitigation Strategies." *Journal of Energy Storage* 73: 108875.

⁵³ Kaur, Gurbinder, and Byron D Gates. 2022. "Surface Coatings for Cathodes in Lithium Ion Batteries: From Crystal Structures to Electrochemical Performance." *Journal of The Electrochemical Society* 169 (4): 43504.

⁵⁴ Xin, Fengxia, Hui Zhou, Xiaobo Chen, Mateusz Zuba, Natasha Chernova, Guangwen Zhou, and M. Stanley Whittingham. 2019. "Li-Nb-O Coating/Substitution Enhances the Electrochemical Performance of the $\text{LiNi}_0.8\text{Mn}_0.1\text{Co}_0.1\text{O}_2$ (NMC 811) Cathode." *ACS Applied Materials and Interfaces* 11 (38): 34889–94. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.9b09696>.

Solvent recovery and recycling may improve the environmental footprint of wet coating techniques. The often-used toxic NMP has strict emission regulations^{55,56}, with recovery rates of around 70-80% in the battery industry. This material is usually reused, with losses estimated to be around 20-30%⁵⁷. In the future, it is expected that the next LIB generation will be based on NMC955 (90% Nickel, 5% Manganese and 5% Cobalt) and then on Li-S or Li-air cathodes^{58,59}.

LLZO-LPSCI was selected for the **solid electrolyte**. However, due to the low TRL of hybrid oxide-sulphide SE, the same issues regarding **standardised production** processes also apply to the SE and, consequently, to catholyte manufacturing. Adding a polymer binder to the SE mixing helps to extend the life of the cell by reducing volume variation and providing close contact of the materials together, aiding the binder present in the catholyte⁶⁰. Additionally, increasing the thickness of the electrolyte by applying maximum compression while maintaining ionic conductivity can help prevent Li dendrite penetration and extend cell lifetime.

It is important to ensure extended cell lifetime, and one of the main challenges of SSBs is the potential negative reactions between the different cell components within the cell, meaning the interfaces between negative electrode and electrolyte and interfaces between positive electrode and electrolyte. Stable and intimate interfaces are mandatory to ensure long cycle life. Unstable interfaces result from chemical and electrochemical side reactions. In the case of sulphide electrolyte, it is known notably that argyrodite decompose at interface due to strong reduction with Li metal⁶¹. Reduction species may further involve during cycling, resulting in increased contact resistance between Li metal and the solid electrolyte. When the current density exceeds the critical current density during plating or stripping, dendritic lithium deposition will form and cause short circuit. Several strategies are envisioned to mitigate these different

⁵⁵ Sherwood, James, Thomas J Farmer, and James H Clark. 2018. "Catalyst: Possible Consequences of the N-Methyl Pyrrolidone REACH Restriction." *Chem* 4 (9): 2010–12.

⁵⁶ Hogue, Cheryl. 2018. "EU Moves to control NMP, other substances." *C&EN* 96 (7): 14. <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/pdf/10.1021/cen-09607-govcon2>.

⁵⁷ Liu, Yangtao, Ruihan Zhang, Jun Wang, and Yan Wang. 2021. "Current and Future Lithium-Ion Battery Manufacturing." *IScience* 24 (4): 102332. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2021.102332>.

⁵⁸ Batteries Europe. 2020. "Batteries Europe: Strategic Research Agenda for Batteries 2020." European Technology and Innovation Platform. https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/batteries_europe_strategic_research_agenda_december_2020__1.pdf.

⁵⁹ Edström, Kristina, Robert Dominko, Maximilian Fichtner, Thomas Otuszewski, Simon Perraud, Christian Punckt, Jean-marie Tarascon, Tejs Vegge, and Winter Martin. 2021. "BATTERY 2030+Roadmap: Inventing the Sustainable Batteries of the Future." https://battery2030.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/c_860904-l_1-k_roadmap-27-march.pdf.

⁶⁰ Khomein, Piyachai, Young Woon Byeon, Dongye Liu, Jin Yu, Andrew M. Minor, Haegyeom Kim, and Gao Liu. 2023. "Lithium Phosphorus Sulfide Chloride-Polymer Composite via the Solution-Precipitation Process for Improving Stability toward Dendrite Formation of Li-Ion Solid Electrolyte." *ACS Applied Materials and Interfaces* 15 (9): 11723–30. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.2c21302>.

⁶¹ Pang, Bo, Yongping Gan, Yang Xia, Hui Huang, Xinping He, and Wenkui Zhang. 2022. "Regulation of the Interfaces between Argyrodite Solid Electrolytes and Lithium Metal Anode." *Frontiers in Chemistry* 10: 837978.

issues, such as coating of Li metal with appropriate material in order to have designed interphase with high ionic conductivity and low electronic conductivity⁶².

Regarding manufacturing options, direct coating of hybrid solid-state electrolyte onto the cathode can help reduce the thickness of the obtained catholyte and avoid the need for a separate production line, increasing **material and energy efficiency**. Furthermore, in the ADVAGEN, the direct coating process will be applied on the NMC811 strip, add an easy handling factor during assembly as it will eliminate the additional stacking procedure for hybrid solid-state electrolyte and the cathode. The simultaneous experiments to upscale the process were continuously assessed. The thickness of the electrolyte should correspond to a balance between not extending the Li-ion pathway (affects transport resistance) and preventing dendrite formation. The electrolyte should be as thin as possible to reduce the resistance, therefore improve the performance, and meet the gravimetric and volumetric energy requirement, but thick enough to provide resistance to dendrites penetration and therefore failure of the cell.

Safety issues rely on the sulphide part of the electrolyte as it reacts violently with water. Therefore, it is recommended that the hybrid solid-state electrolyte be manufactured and processed in a dry room with H₂O and H₂S sensors to ensure a **safe manufacturing environment** (e.g., dry/clean room class ISO 7)^{63,64}. Working with specific automated production lines and limited number of technical operators can also limit the risk level and increase safety. The oxide material can be handled more safely due to its lower reactivity, but a dry atmosphere is also required during storage.

The ADVAGEN cell will have a Li-M **anode** that requires dry air/vacuum packaging before the cutting and assembly process for **safety** concerns. This anode will allow for **higher capacity**, which are considered advantageous for electric mobility applications. The combination of the Li-M with the SE can suppress the formation of dendrites and **increase the lifetime of the SSB cell**, and at the same time, Li-M could **increase the overall battery cell capacity** when compared with graphite and silicon^{65,66,67,68}. It is also recommended to add a protective layer on the Li-M (Al₂O₃/LiF/Li₃N/etc.) to improve interfacial connections and avoid Li-dendrite penetration from anode to the hybrid SSE interface and improve the longevity of the cell. The maturation of Li-M manufacturing processes can provide a significant reduction in **energy consumption**

⁶² Su, Han, Yu Liu, Yu Zhong, Jingru Li, Xiuli Wang, Xinhui Xia, Changdong Gu, and Jiangping Tu. 2022. "Stabilizing the Interphase between Li and Argrodite Electrolyte through Synergistic Phosphating Process for All-Solid-State Lithium Batteries." *Nano Energy* 96: 107104.

⁶³ Heimes, Heiner, Achim Kampker, Sarah Wennemar, Artur Scheibe, Jan Felix Plumeyer, Sarah Michaelis, and Jörg Schtrumpf. 2023. "Production of an All-Solid-State Battery Cell." Aachen. https://www.pem.rwth-aachen.de/global/show_document.asp?id=aaaaaaaaabwfsvdl.

⁶⁴ Heimes, Heiner, Achim Kampker, Christian Offermanns, Nikolaus Lackner, Timon Elliger, Valentin Mussehl, Sarah Michaelis, and Jennifer Zienow. 2023. "Production Process of a Lithium-Ion Battery Cell." Aachen. https://www.pem.rwth-aachen.de/global/show_document.asp?id=aaaaaaaaabyilawq.

⁶⁵ Zhu, Bin, Xinyu Wang, Pengcheng Yao, Jinlei Li, and Jia Zhu. 2019. "Towards High Energy Density Lithium Battery Anodes: Silicon and Lithium." *Chemical Science* 10 (30): 7132–48.

⁶⁶ Wang, Renheng, Weisheng Cui, Fulu Chu, and Feixiang Wu. 2020. "Lithium Metal Anodes: Present and Future." *Journal of Energy Chemistry* 48: 145–59.

⁶⁷ Niu, Junjie, and Shuai Kang. 2019. "New High-Energy Anode Materials."

⁶⁸ Eftekhari, Ali. 2019. *Future Lithium-Ion Batteries*. Royal Society of Chemistry.

and costs during production^{69,70}. Nonetheless, future SSB systems are expected to be “anode-free”. The main concept Li-M on Cu will not be introduced in the production step. However, the plating of Li-M on the anode current collector (Cu) will form during initial lithiation process. **Eliminating Li-M coating process during manufacturing can reduce the amount of wasted lithium materials** in the SSB anode production process⁷¹.

Due to the high volatility of the materials, it is recommended that the **assembly** process occur quickly to ensure the highest **quality** possible. As such, each component should be manufactured in the same plant site to avoid quality degradation and prevent transport-related **costs and environmental impacts**.

When compared with current 3rd generation LIB, SSB technology already brings advantages regarding reduced volume and weight for the same capacity, which will reduce emissions related to packaging. This lower volume will also allow more free space within the car for other systems and features in a car. Nonetheless, the format of SSB cells can be optimised for even lower material consumption and optimal performance. There are several types of potential cell design (e.g., cylindrical, prismatic and pouch) for liquid electrolyte LIBs, however, for SSB technology, the prismatic and pouch cells are considered to be the most applicable. The pouch **cell format** was chosen for its **low volume and high gravimetric energy density, and generally more cost-effective**. This selection does not affect the performance of the battery system and still allows for variability, innovation and competitiveness through the several possible pouch sizes for several end-uses (i.e., small, medium and large vehicles for short and long-range vehicle autonomy)^{72,73}. The well-established pouch cell materials do not provide obstacles during production and processing, resulting in **reduced cell weight and good recyclability**. In addition, this cell design does not also affect the installation of the battery system in the vehicle. As such, it is recommended for pouch cells to be in the standardised SSB cell format. This will facilitate the development of standardised production (with standard components), testing, second-life and recycling processes with potential economic benefits for all stakeholders, including end-users. Nonetheless, it is recommended that the assembly line allow for **flexibility** so that the components can be adapted for prismatic cell formats. The envisioned SSB production and system design considers **modularity** to increase or decrease the capacity according to its intended use. More layers can be stacked to increase the cell's capacity without further changing the chemistries, design or production process when the optimised design setup is established.

During production, several **waste** generation streams occur, either in stamping the cathode and anode (5% material loss), sputtering (10% estimated material loss), cathode cutting, or non-compliant material (e.g., lithium requires high purity levels to manufacture the Li-M anode, generating waste when these

⁶⁹ Han, Zhiyuan, Chen Zhang, Qiaowei Lin, Yunbo Zhang, Yaqian Deng, Junwei Han, Dingcai Wu, Feiyu Kang, Quan-Hong Yang, and Wei Lv. 2021. “A Protective Layer for Lithium Metal Anode: Why and How.” *Small Methods* 5 (4): 2001035.

⁷⁰ Li, Jiawei, Zhao Kong, Xiaoxi Liu, Bocong Zheng, Qi Hua Fan, Elias Garratt, Thomas Schuelke, Keliang Wang, Hui Xu, and Hong Jin. 2021. “Strategies to Anode Protection in Lithium Metal Battery: A Review.” *InfoMat* 3 (12): 1333–63.

⁷¹ Wen, Jiayun, Tengrui Wang, Chao Wang, Yiming Dai, Zhenyou Song, Xuyang Liu, Qian Yu, et al. 2024. “A Tailored Interface Design for Anode-Free Solid-State Batteries.” *Advanced Materials* 36 (6): 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202307732>.

⁷² Niu, Chaojiang, Hongkyung Lee, Shuru Chen, Qiuyan Li, Jason Du, Wu Xu, Ji-Guang Zhang, M Stanley Whittingham, Jie Xiao, and Jun Liu. 2019. “High-Energy Lithium Metal Pouch Cells with Limited Anode Swelling and Long Stable Cycles.” *Nature Energy* 4 (7): 551–59.

⁷³ Chen, Shuru, Chaojiang Niu, Hongkyung Lee, Qiuyan Li, Lu Yu, Wu Xu, Ji-Guang Zhang, et al. 2019. “Critical Parameters for Evaluating Coin Cells and Pouch Cells of Rechargeable Li-Metal Batteries.” *Joule* 3 (4): 1094–1105.

requirements are not met). Usually, this production scrap also includes electrodes and full cells that do not meet requirements, making them easier to recycle as they don't have cables, collectors or casing (low contamination from plastics and no need to disassemble the battery). As such, production scrap is considered to have higher quality as recycling feedstock than EoL batteries. These high-quality materials are easier to reintegrate into the production line, creating an opportunity for manufacturers to recover this continuous stream from their production process (10% of the production material goes to scrap⁷⁴), avoiding waste generation and waste treatment costs. The establishment of symbiotic relationships with recycling facilities coupled with the application of industrial ecology principles^{75,76} can support the recovery of these valuable materials that are still in high-quality condition.

To conclude, the main challenges for cell design and manufacturing are related to balancing costs and sustainability with the limited availability of secondary sources to meet regulatory requirements and reduce carbon footprint. Manufacturing optimization of the cathode regarding formulation and processes for optimal energy and material efficiency is necessary while low-to-none cobalt chemistries (e.g., NMC955, Li-S and Li-air) are still in development. The SE formulation alternatives are still vast, and standardized processes are still in development for high quality and safe SE production. The interface challenges between SE and cathode are also important to ensure longer cell life. The Li-M anode provides high-performing cells, but requires special focus on safety measures when handling and potential unwanted reactions in the interface with the catholyte materials. The SSB cell format can be standardized if the cell assembly production process is flexible to other variations, when necessary, but this step also lacks standardized processes for large-scale SSB cell manufacturing.

3.1.2. Module-to-pack-to-market ecodesign considerations

Although the module-to-pack step is not included in the ADVAGEN project scope, its assessment is important to be included to ensure an overall SSB final design and performance that is in line with the ecodesign principles. For the **module**, the number of cells can be increased or decreased to adapt to end-user requirements, and the number of modules in the SSB pack can also be added to increase the battery system capacity. The pouch cell stack pressure in the module should be maintained, since the impact of the pressure for the operability of cell during charge-discharge to prevent high amount of swelling is essential^{77,78,79}. The ADVAGEN module will also include several options for the internal jig/cell spacer inside the module. The options are: (1) spring-based spacer; (2) plate-based spacer; or (3) hybrid, which will be

⁷⁴ Yu, Lu, Yaocai Bai, Bryant Polzin, and Ilias Belharouak. 2024. "Unlocking the Value of Recycling Scrap from Li-Ion Battery Manufacturing: Challenges and Outlook." *Journal of Power Sources* 593 (August 2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2023.233955>.

⁷⁵ Ehrenfeld, J, and N Gertler. 1997. "Industrial Ecology in Practice: The Evolution of Interdependence at Kalundborg" 1 (1): 67–79. <https://doi.org/10.1162/jiec.1997.1.1.67>.

⁷⁶ Despeisse, M., P. D. Ball, S. Evans, and A. Levers. 2012. "Industrial Ecology at Factory Level - A Conceptual Model." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 31: 30–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2012.02.027>.

⁷⁷ Zhang, Fengyu, Yunna Guo, Liqiang Zhang, Peng Jia, Xiang Liu, Ping Qiu, Hongbing Zhang, and Jianyu Huang. 2023. "A Review of the Effect of External Pressure on All-Solid-State Batteries." *Etransportation* 15: 100220.

⁷⁸ Tan, Darren H S, Ying Shirley Meng, and Jihyun Jang. 2022. "Scaling up High-Energy-Density Sulfidic Solid-State Batteries: A Lab-to-Pilot Perspective." *Joule* 6 (8): 1755–69.

⁷⁹ Lee, Chanhee, Sang Yun Han, John A Lewis, Pralav P Shetty, David Yeh, Yuhgene Liu, Emily Klein, Hyun-Wook Lee, and Matthew T McDowell. 2021. "Stack Pressure Measurements to Probe the Evolution of the Lithium--Solid-State Electrolyte Interface." *ACS Energy Letters* 6 (9): 3261–69.

demonstrated later in WP6, using either metal-based or polymeric 3D-printed spacer in the module demonstrator to fixate the pressure inside the cell and avoid unwanted swelling, ensuring **safety and increased lifetime**.

The **battery pack** is also important to ensure efficient and cost-effective battery disassembly. Reducing the number of screws and welded parts, as well as the use of adhesives, can improve the disassembly step, where the information regarding the defined structure is available in the battery passport^{80,6}. Recent trends in battery pack design have considered also eliminating modules to develop cell-to-pack structures. This approach could bring benefits for disassembly as well as reducing the number of materials and the overall battery system weight. However, the module is a crucial structure to ensure cell longevity by providing mechanical protection and an integrated battery management system (BMS) that ensures thermal management and proper functioning^{81,82,83}. Module assembly plays a key role in protecting the cells from shock and vibration that occur during vehicle operation. In addition, modules ensure the battery pack's **modularity and adaptability for repair, reuse and remanufacturing**^{84,85,86,87}. An EV LIB pack system, after its first life in electric mobility, can be opened to add (or remove) modules for continuing its first life or, if not possible, for second-life applications with different requirements (e.g., capacity, lifetime or size) and recycling. This provides easy and efficient integration into other **second-life applications** as handling and testing one unit module is simpler than handling and testing hundreds of single cells. Testing modules instead of all cells in a battery pack thus allows to reduce time and resources as well as costs for the intermediate stage between first and second life, and increase potential material recovery.

When the technology reaches the **market level**, it is expected that the technological development and design trends will be influenced by original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) and their positioning in the battery value chain. In-house battery manufacturing has been discussed as the next step for several main carmakers, such as Toyota, Tesla and General Motors, with the goal of securing a steady battery supply for electric vehicle manufacturing and facilitating battery customisation according to each car model and

⁸⁰ Lander, Laura, Chris Tagnon, Viet Nguyen-Tien, Emma Kendrick, Robert J.R. Elliott, Andrew P. Abbott, Jacqueline S. Edge, and Gregory J. Offer. 2023. "Breaking It down: A Techno-Economic Assessment of the Impact of Battery Pack Design on Disassembly Costs." *Applied Energy* 331 (December 2022): 120437. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2022.120437>.

⁸¹ Lee, Ungki, Namwoo Kang, and Yoon Koo Lee. 2023. "Optimization of Module Structure Considering Mechanical and Thermal Safety of Pouch Cell Lithium-Ion Batteries Using a Reliability-Based Design Optimization Approach." *Journal of Energy Storage* 72: 108650.

⁸² Heimes, Heiner, Achim Kampker, Saskia Wessel, and Mario Kehrer. 2019. "Battery Module and Pack Assembly Process." https://www.vdma.org/documents/7411591/15357859/Production+module+and+pack_eng/6188ab6d-5411-e348-0f88-c9f0276079a4.

⁸³ Schmidt, Simon, Jan Clausen, Robin van der Auwera, Oliver Klapp, Rico Schmerler, David Löffler, Maximilian Jakob Werner, and Lukas Block. 2022. "Novel Battery Module Design for Increased Resource Efficiency." *World Electric Vehicle Journal* 13 (10). <https://doi.org/10.3390/wevj13100177>.

⁸⁴ Kim, Kyunghyun, and Jung-Il Choi. 2023. "Effect of Cell-to-Cell Variation and Module Configuration on the Performance of Lithium-Ion Battery Systems." *Applied Energy* 352: 121888.

⁸⁵ He, Liange, Zihan Gu, Yan Zhang, Haodong Jing, and Pengpai Li. 2023. "Review on Thermal Management of Lithium-Ion Batteries for Electric Vehicles: Advances, Challenges, and Outlook." *Energy & Fuels* 37 (7): 4835–57.

⁸⁶ Liu, Wei, Tobias Placke, and K T Chau. 2022. "Overview of Batteries and Battery Management for Electric Vehicles." *Energy Reports* 8: 4058–84.

⁸⁷ Singh, Bharat, Deepanshu Rawat, Pulkesh Parwani, Rhydham Gupta, and Tisha Kapoor. 2022. "Design and Control of Battery Management System for Electric Vehicle." In *International Conference on Flexible Electronics for Electric Vehicles*, 277–84.

specifications⁸⁸. This trend can support more innovation strategies for battery technology but can also lead to even more diversification of battery designs in the system. Although the new battery regulation has established common requirements for more sustainable battery design, there are still many gaps when it comes to design decisions with the purpose of enabling innovation. As such, it is recommended that carmakers participate in **joint efforts** with R&D stakeholders and battery recycling companies **to support and aid in the development of standardisation and best available techniques (BAT)** for SSB design and manufacturing, including **cell and module labelling** (in line with the digital battery passport⁶), to create a common pathway for more efficient and circular battery manufacturing.

In summary, the main design difficulties identified for SSB module-to-pack are based on the trade-offs between safety for disassembly and performance, as well as modularity and material efficiency for extended lifetime. The gaps in regulation for SSB technology and the design variability are also important challenges.

3.1.3. Second-life applications and recycling

After production, **testing** SSB cells to validate their performance poses a challenge due to difficulties in pressure maintenance, conductivity issues and mechanical and technical considerations. Currently, standard tests are based on the pressure levels from 3rd generation LIBs (liquid electrolyte and graphite-based anode). One typical indicator of the SoH of the battery (useful also to assess if the battery is suitable for second life), as described, for example, in the standard UL1974, is the internal resistance test. This test consists of applying repetitive current pulses at very high C-rates. However, this procedure is quite difficult to apply to SSB as the cell polarisation gets very high. Potentiostatic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (PEIS) can give some information about the overall cell resistance and its evolution with time. Coupled with the capacity tests (as described in UL1974), it might be enough to assess the SoH^{89,90,91}.

International platforms (EU Battery Alliance, Batteries EU, IPCEI) are focusing on the growing need for designing standards that allow easy disassembly, effective labelling, and effective and detailed tracking of the single battery use within the EV operation. **Standardising the battery State of Health (SoH)** definition is also a relevant ongoing discussion (currently, battery manufacturers use their own proprietary definition), which is also necessary for SSB technology^{92,93}. Indeed, a retired battery pack is not ideal for

⁸⁸ International Energy Agency. 2023. "Global EV Outlook 2023 - Catching up with Climate Ambitions." <https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/dacf14d2-eabc-498a-8263-9f97fd5dc327/GEVO2023.pdf>.

⁸⁹ Hong, Jichao, Zhenpo Wang, Wen Chen, Leyi Wang, Peng Lin, and Changhui Qu. 2021. "Online Accurate State of Health Estimation for Battery Systems on Real-World Electric Vehicles with Variable Driving Conditions Considered." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 294: 125814. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.125814>.

⁹⁰ Braco, Elisa, Idoia San Martín, Pablo Sanchis, Alfredo Ursúa, and Daniel-Ioan Stroe. 2022. "State of Health Estimation of Second-Life Lithium-Ion Batteries under Real Profile Operation." *Applied Energy* 326: 119992. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2022.119992>.

⁹¹ Montes, Tomás, Maite Etxandi-Santolaya, Josh Eichman, Victor José Ferreira, Lluís Trilla, and Cristina Corchero. 2022. "Procedure for Assessing the Suitability of Battery Second Life Applications after EV First Life." *Batteries* 8 (9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries8090122>.

⁹² Rufino Júnior, Carlos Antônio, Eleonora Riva Sanseverino, Pierluigi Gallo, Daniel Koch, Sergej Diel, Gero Walter, Lluís Trilla, et al. 2024. "Towards to Battery Digital Passport: Reviewing Regulations and Standards for Second-Life Batteries." *Batteries* 10 (4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries10040115>.

⁹³ Hossain, Eklas, Darren Murtaugh, Jaisen Mody, Hossain Mansur Resalat Faruque, Md Samiul Haque Sunny, and Naeem Mohammad. 2019. "A Comprehensive Review on Second-Life Batteries: Current State, Manufacturing Considerations,

direct reuse straight from a vehicle. While the retired batteries have enticing economic advantages, they cannot be integrated into other applications in their current state. Several considerations applicable to the aging system necessitate provisional screening procedures in order to assess battery characteristics that are appropriate⁹⁴.

Finally, for **transportation**, it is recommended that each battery system be transported to end-user applications (or for second-life applications) with testing results that showcase its chemistry, current condition and integrity⁹⁵, alongside compliance with the ADR (European Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Road) requirements⁹⁶. The materials used for safe handling during transportation must be light, non-flammable, and have good shock absorption capabilities to ensure **safety and low environmental impact related to packaging**.

When EV batteries reach their **end of life** (e.g., maintaining 80% of total usable capacity and a resting self-discharge rate of around 5% over a 24-hour period), manufacturers can consider, before recycling, **second-life applications where the reduced performance capabilities are still valuable** (for example, short-range vehicles, stationary use)⁹⁷. In the case of SSBs with Li-M anodes, the first challenge is understanding if the same criteria would be applicable (80% of the nominal capacity) and if such batteries would guarantee an acceptable safety level for second-life applications. Ageing characterisation, as well as safety testing, could be performed, particularly focusing on cells/modules with a capacity lower than 80% of the nominal capacity that could be candidates for second-life. The aim would be to gain data about the reliability of metallic lithium SSB, as understanding the condition of the EOL battery is crucial before transportation and storage.

The continuous quantification and monitoring of the parameters that characterise the state of SSBs can support the development of quality parameters for sorting to either second-life or recycling⁹⁸. Together with standardising the SSB pack design, this can ensure a more efficient sorting and recycling process, as

Applications, Impacts, Barriers Potential Solutions, Business Strategies, and Policies.” IEEE Access 7: 73215–52. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2917859>.

⁹⁴ Shahjalal, Mohammad, Probir Kumar Roy, Tamanna Shams, Ashley Fly, Jahedul Islam Chowdhury, Md Rishad Ahmed, and Kailong Liu. 2022. “A Review on Second-Life of Li-Ion Batteries: Prospects, Challenges, and Issues.” Energy 241: 122881. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.122881>.

⁹⁵ Lisbona, Diego, and Timothy Snee. 2011. “A Review of Hazards Associated with Primary Lithium and Lithium-Ion Batteries.” Process Safety and Environmental Protection 89 (6): 434–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2011.06.022>.

⁹⁶ ADR. 2023. “ADR 2023 - Agreement Concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Road.” <https://unece.org/transport/standards/transport/dangerous-goods/adr-2023-agreement-concerning-international-carriage>.

⁹⁷ Caldani, Saverio, Irene Macchiarelli, Benedikt Unger, and Victor Olsen. 2024. “Challenges & Opportunities of Repurposing.”

⁹⁸ Illa Font, Carlos Henrique, Hugo Valadares Siqueira, João Eustáquio Machado Neto, João Lucas Ferreira dos Santos, Sergio Luiz Stevan, Attilio Converti, and Fernanda Cristina Corrêa. 2023. “Second Life of Lithium-Ion Batteries of Electric Vehicles: A Short Review and Perspectives.” Energies 16 (2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16020953>.

already studied for the 3rd generation^{99,100,101}. When it comes to recycling efficiency, **disassembly to the electrode level** would be ideal for reaching the established 65 wt.% target by the Battery Regulation⁶, supported by more automated systems based on the standardised design, including the recovery of other materials beyond the CAM, such as from the anode, the electrolyte and the casing, supported by more automated systems based on the standardised design.

Recycling conventional liquid-electrolyte batteries at an industrial scale involves pyrometallurgical and mechanical pre-processing methods. In the pyrometallurgical process, an alloy is formed, from which valuable metals can be recovered using hydrometallurgical techniques. In the mechanical pre-processing method, a "black mass" containing active materials from the cathode and anode is generated by shredding the cells and sorting the finest particles. However, these approaches are not suitable for SSBs¹⁰². In the pyrometallurgical process, the formation of an alloy hinders the recovery of valuable compounds such as the solid electrolyte. In the mechanical pre-processing method, the presence of the solid electrolyte prevents the "black mass" from being separated by simple mechanical sorting, as it cannot be evaporated like liquid electrolytes. Additionally, the sticky nature of the Li-M anode complicates sorting. Therefore, the most efficient method for recycling SSBs with high recovery rates involves cell disassembly to the electrode level.

The Battery Regulation also established by 2027 a recycling efficiency of 90% for cobalt, 90% for copper, 90% for nickel, and 50% for lithium. These targets can be achievable for 3rd generation LIBs by using conventional techniques, except for lithium, due to the low economic feasibility of the processes on an industrial scale. In the proposed SSB design, Li is mostly present in the Li-M anode, which may need a different treatment due to its easy reaction and bonding with other materials. An effective separation process of Li-M from the other metals will allow for easier recovery of lithium with high levels of purity, achieving the established target. The increased availability of these materials will allow the closing of the loop of critical and strategic materials and allow the reduction of external dependencies on high-risk countries, as well as reduce potential risks regarding production costs, securing a circular battery value chain.

Summarizing, testing challenges rely on lack of standard procedures for SSB technology that can allow for SoH measures, which is crucial for the other life cycle stages, such as use, second-life applications, transport and recycling. The second-life criteria for most LIB of 80% may not be applicable for SSB, and further research is necessary on these parameters that support decision-making for handling battery applications. The reliability and safety ageing of SSB needs also further testing to ensure proper handling. In addition, disassembly and recycling processes currently used are not applicable for SSBs due to the SE

⁹⁹ Haram, Mohammed Hussein Saleh Mohammed, Jia Woon Lee, Gobbi Ramasamy, Eng Eng Ngu, Siva Priya Thiagarajah, and Yuen How Lee. 2021. "Feasibility of Utilising Second Life EV Batteries: Applications, Lifespan, Economics, Environmental Impact, Assessment, and Challenges." *Alexandria Engineering Journal*. Elsevier B.V. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aej.2021.03.021>.

¹⁰⁰ Shahjalal, Mohammad, Probir Kumar Roy, Tamanna Shams, Ashley Fly, Jahedul Islam Chowdhury, Md Rishad Ahmed, and Kailong Liu. 2022. "A Review on Second-Life of Li-Ion Batteries: Prospects, Challenges, and Issues." *Energy* 241: 122881. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.122881>.

¹⁰¹ Dong, Qingyin, Shuang Liang, Jinhui Li, Hyung Chul Kim, Wei Shen, and Timothy J. Wallington. 2023. "Cost, Energy, and Carbon Footprint Benefits of Second-Life Electric Vehicle Battery Use." *IScience* 26 (7): 107195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2023.107195>.

¹⁰² Azhari, Luqman, Sungyool Bong, Xiaotu Ma, and Yan Wang. 2020. "Recycling for All Solid-State Lithium-Ion Batteries." *Matter* 3 (6): 1845–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matt.2020.10.027>.

and Li-M anode. It is expected that standardized design and the battery passport will support stakeholders in these stages to achieve the established regulatory targets.

3.1.4. *Conflicting Recommendations*

Some of the provided recommendations may bring benefits for some parameters while simultaneously limiting the application of other parameters or negatively affecting the final design. This section aims to explain the positioning of the ADVAGEN project regarding the identified potential conflicting recommendations.

One of the most evident potential conflicts is the incentive for second-life applications versus the recycling of batteries in order to obtain secondary streams to increase the circularity of the battery value chain. The availability of material from post-consumer waste batteries is expected to increase as current EV batteries in use reach the end of their useful life. However, the increased longevity in SSB technology coupled with the development of battery second-life applications can delay this stream and create constraints on reaching the recycled content targets established by the new Battery Regulation. The current literature states that redirecting LIBs to second-life applications has more environmental benefits¹⁰³ as it extends the useful life of the battery. To determine whether SSBs can be repurposed for a second life, minimum performance parameters should be established. This involves setting a performance limit based on parameters such as capacity, state of health (SoH), and safety considerations, where SSBs that fall below this limit should be sent for recycling.

Another potential recommendation conflict relies on the increase of battery longevity and performance versus the reduction of the variety of materials and the minimisation of critical raw materials. Reducing the number of different materials is a complicated task in battery products, as most materials are selected for their potential to improve battery performance and safety while considering the respective costs and environmental impacts. However, the use of critical and strategic raw materials³³ such as lithium, manganese, graphite, nickel and cobalt are directly linked to the battery product and policy regulations are limiting the use of these raw materials. As such, in order to reduce the consumption of CRM in the battery value chain, these materials should be used for more demanding technical performance requirements, such as long-range electric passenger cars and electric trucks, where the increased durability of the SSB system is guaranteed due to the higher capacity already required for the first life.

Recycled CRM should be prioritized to minimize the overall impacts of the SSB cell. For short-range vehicles and lower performance requirements, due to their shorter durability (even when considering second-life applications), the use of CRM should be reduced whenever possible without compromising overall safety. This will allow a stricter focus on CRM in high-level performance applications with high longevity in the first life and various potential uses in the second life. Nonetheless, further research should be conducted to further decrease the dependence on these materials, through potential non-critical substitutes and increased availability of recycled material.

Lastly, it is important to acknowledge that pursuing higher performance targets for SSBs can also increase safety concerns. In the case of Li-M anodes and sulphide-containing SEs, the high-performing SSB cell system brings safety challenges during production and disassembly due to the high reactivity of these

¹⁰³ Tao, Yanqiu, Christopher D. Rahn, Lynden A. Archer, and Fengqi You. 2021. "Second Life and Recycling: Energy and Environmental Sustainability Perspectives for High-Performance Lithium-Ion Batteries." *Science Advances* 7 (45): 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abi7633>.

materials. With the robust safety measures previously mentioned, the production system can manage and reduce the associated risk to ensure the safe production of high-quality SSB cells. In addition, the information provided by the upcoming digital battery passport (mandatory in 2027) will provide battery dismantlers and battery recyclers with detailed information regarding the composition of the battery components, including cathode, anode and electrolyte⁶, allowing them to integrate this information into the disassembly system, in an automated manner, and provide the necessary safety measures for the safe disassembly of SSB packs.

4. Ecodesign Guidelines for solid-state batteries

4.1 Guidelines

Based on the collected information from the literature and the recommendations provided by partners, this section presents the ecodesign guidelines for SSB technology development and application, based on the defined ecodesign parameters. These guidelines are to be considered by ADVAGEN partners throughout the development of the SSB cell and module. Following this scope, major action points can be integrated regarding the ecodesign of cell and module materials, as well as production processes aligned with laboratorial-level expectations (see guidelines 1, 3, 8 to 19, 21 to 23, and 26). The following ecodesign parameters application are labelled by colour to match with the guideline's application.

[CAPACITY | DURABILITY | SAFETY AND QUALITY] | [CRM | ENVIRONMENTAL AND COST IMPACTS]

1. For high **capacity** and **reduced environmental and cost impacts**, **reduced material and energy consumption**, **reduced waste**, and **reduced CRM**: Minimise the amount of cobalt present in the cathode without compromising capacity – selection of NMC811 or NMC955. Further research is needed for Li-air and Li-S cathode development;
2. For **reduced environmental and cost impacts**, **reduced material and energy consumption**, **reduced waste**, and **reduced CRM**, establish symbiotic partnerships between battery recycling stakeholders and manufacturers to allow for production scrap recircularization back to the production line, alongside with reintegration of recycled materials from battery waste, considering industrial ecology principles;
3. For **reduced environmental and cost impacts**, **reduced material and energy consumption**, **reduced waste**, and **reduced CRM**, optimise energy and resource efficiency in solid electrolyte and catholyte production, develop BAT and standardise the manufacturing process (NMC 811 or 955) for the minimum amount and minimum variety of CRM, with incorporation of recycled materials;
4. For **reduced environmental and cost impacts**, **reduced material and energy consumption**, **reduced waste**, and **reduced CRM**, incorporate recycled material content into the raw materials production at the ore refining stage, to allow producers to buy CAM raw materials that already fulfil the regulatory requirements for battery recycled content, with the incorporated amounts made available to be integrated into the digital passport of the final battery product to enable value chain traceability.
5. For high **capacity**, **durability** and **reduced environmental and cost impacts**, **reduced material and energy consumption**, **reduced waste**, and **reduced CRM**, CRM should be prioritized for high-performing applications such as long-range electric passenger cars and electric trucks. Recycled CRM should be prioritised. In short-range vehicles with lower performance requirements, the use of CRM should be reduced whenever possible without compromising overall safety. In addition, further research should be conducted on potential non-critical material substitutes for SSB CRM;
6. For **reduced environmental and cost impacts**, **reduced material and energy consumption**, and

- reduced waste, introduce digital monitoring tools into the manufacturing and assembly lines that consider technical, safety, environmental and cost parameters for continuous monitoring;
7. For **safety and quality**, reduced environmental and cost impacts, reduced material and energy consumption, reduced waste, investment and further development of air-to-air systems for the cathode manufacturing process;
 8. For reduced environmental and cost impacts, reduced material and energy consumption, and reduced waste, further development of water-based solvents for cathode coating and wet processing for the cathode and solvent removal;
 9. For high durability SSB cells capacity and safety, include a polymer binder to the SE mixing to reduce volume variation and provide close contact of the materials together;
 10. For high durability SSB cells capacity, reduced environmental impacts and safety, optimize component cell component thickness according to the targeted cost and performance;
 11. For high durability SSB cells and safety, apply a polymer protective layer to reduce interface reactions between the SE and the Li-M anode;
 12. For safety and quality, manufacture, process, and store the SE using specific automated production lines and a small number of technical staff in a dry room with H₂O and H₂S sensors to ensure a safe manufacturing environment (e.g., dry/clean room class ISO 7);
 13. For high durability and capacity in SSB cells, use Li-M anodes for high-level performance SSB pack mobility applications, safeguarding safety measures during manufacturing, disassembly and recycling, with the support of the digital battery passport, while continue further research into alternative anode-free SSB design;
 14. For reduced environmental and cost impacts, reduced material and energy consumption, reduced waste, and reduced CRM, apply further research into the maturation of the manufacturing process of Li-M anodes;
 15. For safety and quality, reduced environmental and cost impacts, reduced material and energy consumption, and reduced waste, conduct the assembly process quickly to ensure the highest quality possible and manufacturing of components in the same location. In addition, assembly should be flexible to handle different cell formats, if necessary, as well as different levels SSB capacities for different applications;
 16. For reduced material and energy consumption, and reduced waste, apply direct coating of SE onto the cathode to reduce the thickness of the obtained catholyte and avoid the need for a separate production line to facilitate assembly;
 17. For high capacity, reduced environmental and cost impacts, reduced material and energy consumption, and reduced waste, define pouch cell as the standard SSB cell format;

18. For high **durability, safety and quality**, the module should remain as an integral part of the SSB pack to ensure cell longevity, and further assess the best alternative internal jig/cell spacer to stabilise the cell pressure and avoid swelling;
19. For **reduced environmental and cost impacts, reduced material and energy consumption, and reduced waste**, SSB packs should be designed with a reduced number of screws and welded parts and include adhesives to improve the disassembly process step. The disassembly to electrode level should be developed for SSB technology, with the support of more automated disassembly systems that operate based on the information provided by the battery passport regarding pack assembly design in an integrated scanning system;
20. For **reduced environmental and cost impacts, reduced material and energy consumption, and reduced waste, safety and quality**, incentivise OEM to establish joint efforts with R&D and recycling stakeholders to support and aid in the development of standardisation and best available techniques (BAT) for SSB design and manufacturing, including cell and module labelling;
21. For **safety and quality**, the definition of SoH of SSB should be standardised, and SoH testing of SSB should be made through internal resistance tests using PEIS testing, coupled with capacity tests;
22. For high **durability, reduced environmental and cost impacts, reduced material and energy consumption, and reduced waste**, based on the ageing characterisation of SSBs, minimum performance parameters should be established for first and second-life applications considering SoH, capacity and safety parameters. Batteries performing below a defined threshold should be sent for recycling;
23. For high **durability, reduced environmental and cost impacts, reduced material and energy consumption, and reduced waste**, second-life applications should be prioritized according to their condition and the corresponding scenario requirements, adapted to SSBs with Li-M.
24. For **reduced environmental and cost impacts, reduced material and energy consumption, and reduced waste, safety and quality**, materials used for safe handling during transportation must be light, non-flammable, and have good shock absorption capabilities, and the condition of the battery must be made available to the transporting entities, ensuring readability of the battery passport for all intermediary players;
25. For **reduced environmental and cost impacts, reduced material and energy consumption, and reduced waste**, recycling systems should recover anode, electrolyte and casing materials, beyond CAM, to achieve the recycling efficiency of 65 wt.%, and increase the availability of these secondary materials to close the loop on critical and strategic materials for SSB technology.

A summary of the guidelines is presented in Figure 5 for each component and main life cycle stage of SSB technology.

ECODESIGN GUIDELINES FOR SOLID-STATE BATTERIES

MANUFACTURING

CATHODE

- Low-to-zero Cobalt amount;
- Coating to increase structural stability and limit surface reactions;
- investment and research of air-to-air systems for the cathode manufacturing process;
- Investigation of water-based solvent for cathode coating and wet processing for cathode and solvent removal;
- Conduct SE direct deposition in the cathode;

ANODE

- Add polymer protective-layer for the surface between electrolyte;
- Use Li-M anodes for high-level performance, safeguarding safety measures during manufacturing, disassembly and recycling, with the support of the digital battery passport;
- Further research into alternative anode-free SSB design;
- Research for the maturation of the manufacturing process of Li-M anodes;

SOLID ELECTROLYTE

- Include a polymer to the SE mixing to reduce volume variation and provide close contact of the materials together;
- Apply a polymer protective layer to reduce interface reactions between the SE and the Li-M anode;
- Manufacture, process, and store the SE using specific automated production lines and a low number of technical staff in a dry room with H₂O and H₂S sensors for safe manufacturing environment;

- Digital monitoring tools for technical, safety, environmental and cost parameters;
- Quick assembly process to ensure the highest quality possible and manufacturing of components in the same location;

ASSEMBLY

- Standardization of the assembly;
- Ensure flexibility to handle different cell formats, if necessary, as well as different levels SSB capacities for different applications;
- Pouch cell should be the standard SSB cell format

MODULE TO PACK

- The module should remain as an integral part of the SSB pack to ensure cell longevity, a adequate spacer to stabilise the cell pressure and avoid swelling;
- Reduce number of screws and welded parts;

- Use of adhesives instead;
- The disassembly to electrode level should be developed for SSB technology, with the support of more automated disassembly systems that operate based on the information provided by the battery passport;

TESTING

- Standardization of SoH testing making use of internal use techniques such as internal resistance tests using PEIS couple with capacity tests;

- Ageing characterisation of SSBs should be further studied to establish minimum performance parameters for first and second-life applications, as well as a recycling threshold, considering SoH, capacity and safety parameters.

TRANSPORT

- Materials used for safe handling during transportation must be light, non-flammable, and have good shock absorption capabilities;

- The condition of the battery must be made available to the transporting entities, ensuring readability of the battery passport in all stages of transport;

END-OF-LIFE

- OEM to establish joint efforts with R&D and recycling stakeholders;
- Recover of anode, electrolyte and casing materials, beyond CAM, to achieve the recycling efficiency of 65 wt.%;

- Establish symbiotic relationships with recycling facilities;
- Second-life applications should be prioritized based in their condition and the corresponding scenario requirements

Figure 5 – ADVAGEN Ecodesign guidelines for SSB design applications.

Conclusion

The deliverable 2.2 provides ecodesign guidelines for the SSB cell design and life cycle. The document introduces the expectations of the 4th generation of lithium-ion batteries with solid-state electrolytes, emphasising the need to develop low environmental impact SSB technology to support a more resilient and cleaner batteries value chain and secure the future of electric mobility as a supporting pathway towards a carbon-neutral transport sector. Ecodesign was presented as an important tool for considering both technical and environmental aspects to improve the overall product performance.

In line with the ADVAGEN Objective 4, the deliverable aimed to provide ecodesign guidelines for the technological development of SSBs to support battery developers, policymakers and stakeholders of the European battery value chain. To do so, a methodological approach framework was presented to develop ecodesign parameters based on current literature on SSB environmental impacts, current and future policies, and regulatory requirements for electric vehicle batteries worldwide.

The results from the literature assessment allowed to conclude that cathode and anode are the main drivers of the total environmental impacts of SSBs, similarly to current LIB generation, due to the constituting materials. More specifically, the use of CRM in SSB cells should be limited to reduce resource depletion, and second-life applications were incentivised. More efficient energy consumption during production, efficient recycling and cell component thickness optimisation are also recommended. Nonetheless, current studies on LCA for SSBs are limited due to the low technology development, limiting primary life cycle data to laboratory scale conditions. As such, the obtained results come with uncertainty regarding the future maturation of the SSB technology, especially regarding Li-M anodes and solid electrolytes composition and manufacturing process. Similarly, recycling processes are estimated on current recycling systems that do not consider future development because of digitalisation and automation. Cost reduction recommendations focused on drying process and solvent recovery, mentioning also the digitalisation of the manufacturing and assembly processes. Increasing the cell capacity to improve durability and mitigate the environmental and cost impacts from production was also mentioned. The economic viability of recycling is directly dependent on the recycling efficiency of high-value materials of SSBs, specifically in SE and CAM components. From the recommendations obtained in the literature, several key takeaways were identified for ecodesign strategies to reduce environmental impacts.

In the regulatory trends assessment, the upcoming ecodesign regulation provided a framework to develop product-specific ecodesign regulations, which did not provide specific requirements for batteries. Nonetheless, several parameters were identified as potentially applicable to SSB technology and life cycle. Overall, it was concluded that the new battery regulation and the new upcoming ecodesign regulation would play an important role in sustainable battery technology development by providing minimal ecological requirements. From these documents, several action domains were identified where specific ecodesign parameters were established. Considering other regulatory trends outside of the EU, common trends were identified, such as considering the performance of the battery in all of the life cycle stages, promoting energy efficiency, resource conservation and waste reduction. Other common goals, such as sustainable manufacturing, digital labelling, and increased management of EoL batteries for CRM recycling

and recovery were also identified.

From both these documents, were identified dominant topics as: resource efficiency (materials, water and energy), recycling content and efficiency, durability, second-life, environmental impact, emissions and waste generation, labelling and information requirements

While the Battery Directive and Ecodesign Directive offer a foundation for sustainable product design, a more nuanced approach specific to electric vehicle (EV) batteries is necessary. The broad scope of the Battery Directive across various battery types limits its effectiveness in addressing critical aspects for EV batteries, as per example: material selection, recycling requirements, safety measures for transport, first life extension, second life. Further exploration of these topics will contribute to a more robust and thorough understanding of sustainable product design principles.

The supply and cost risks associated with battery critical and strategic materials evidenced the need for active international cooperation to promote fair trade and minimise the effects on developing countries that are part of the value chain. The dependencies on external supply are also being tackled by the EU and the USA through further investment in domestic extraction and processing activities to obtain battery-grade materials, alongside with battery manufacturing.

Based on the analysed regulation, the main ecodesign parameters were selected, focusing on standardizing actions, reduction of CRM, environmental and economic impact reduction, increased capacity and durability, symbiotic industry relationships, and safety measures. These parameters were presented to ADVAGEN partners to define strategies improving the ADVAGEN SSB cell design. It was evidenced that the challenges facing SSB design on a technological level are furthered enhanced with the increased pressure for more sustainable batteries with low carbon footprint and high performance. Nonetheless, the main technical and market challenges that are influenced by these parameters were identified together with design recommendations to improve these parameters in the SSB cell design and the SSB life cycle. From these recommendations, several guidelines were established, considering the product design level challenges for SSBs, namely components, cell, module and pack level to achieve the Objective 4 of ADVAGEN project.

Following the ADVAGEN scope, partners can implement specific action points in SSB cell and module development, considering laboratorial-level expectations (guidelines 1, 3, 8 to 19, 21 to 23, and 26). In addition, guidelines were also provided considering the entire life cycle of the SSB cell, considering the influence of processing, transport, disassembly and recycling systems in the overall environmental performance of SSBs. As such, these guidelines provide an overall guide for building a more sustainable SSB value chain for a greener electric mobility.

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